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CRISTAL

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D5.1 Technical Concept of a Digital Twin

CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modeling
CESNI	European Committee for Drawing up Standards in the field of inland navigation
CNC	Centralized Network Configuration
CoAP	Constrained Application Protocol
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CUC	Centralized User Configuration
CRUD	Create / Read / Update / Delete
CSS	Chirp Spread Spectrum
DBMS	Database management system
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DREAD	Damage / Reproducibility / Exploitability / Affected users / Discoverability
DT	(CRISTAL) Digital Twin
DTLS	Datagram Transport Layer Security
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU-Project)
eMBB	Enhanced mobile Broadband
EPCIS	Electronic Product Code Information Services
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standard Institute
EuRIS	European River Information System
FBG	Fibre Bragg Grating
FCC	Federal Communication Commission
FOS	Fiber Optic Sensors
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GML	Geographical Markup Language
gPTP	Generalized Precision Time Protocol
GPR	Ground-penetrating Radar
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High-performance computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IBS	Intelligent Buoy System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology

ID	Identifier
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronical Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IM	Instant Messaging
IoT	Internet of Things
IPv4, IPv6	Internet Protocol version 4 / 6
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LPWAN	Low Power Wide Area Network
LWT	Last will and Testament (message)
M2M	Machine-to-Machine
MIMO	Multiple Input / Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communication
MoSCoW	Must have / Should have / Could have / Won't have
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MQTT-SN	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport for Sensor Networks
NB-IoT	Narrowband IoT
NDT	Non-Destructive Testing
NFC	Near-field Communication
O&M	Observation & Measurement Standard
OFM	Operation Functionality Monitoring
QoS	Quality of Service
PLM	Product-Lifecycle Management
RA	Reference Architecture
RAM	Random-access memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST	Representational State Transfer
RIS	River Information System
ROM	Read-only memory
RUP	Rational Unified Process
SCMS	Synchro-modal Corridor Management System
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar
SME	Small / Medium sized enterprises
SOSA	Sensor / Observation / Sample / Actuator
SOS	Sensor Observation Service
STRIDE	Spoofing / Tampering / Repudiation / Information disclosure / Denial of service / Elevation of privilege

SSN	Semantic Sensor Network
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TSN	Time Sensitive Networking
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UML	Unified Modeling Language
UWB	Ultra-Wideband
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URL/URI	Uniform Resource Locator/Identifier
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WMAN	Wireless Metropolitan Area Network
WPAN	Wireless Personal Area Network
WWAN	Wireless Wide Area Network
WP	Work Package
XMPP	Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol

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1. Executive Summary

The main objective of WP5 is to develop a digital twin for inland waterway with focus on data analysis, resilience, and smart monitor. The Digital Twin (DT) will represent critical aspects of the inland waterway, with the help of sensor data input from WP7/8/9. The results of the DTs calculations will be visualized, used to generate forecasts, and integrated into an alert system. Maintenance operators will be able to gain insights about the infrastructure, with the help of the Smart Monitor. The Corridor Management System and other external systems will be able to use predictive maintenance and other data driven strategies based on the data analysis and forecasting. Pilot authorities and other involved parties will be able to be notified before a problem occurs on the monitored inland waterway infrastructure. Because of these problems can be solved at an early stage, which will increase the overall resilience of inland waterway transports.

To guide the development of such DT technical requirements and an architecture will be formulated in this deliverable, namely D5.1 Technical Concept of a Digital Twin.

The deliverable was written by the project partner FRA as leader of WP5 and responsible for the development of the DT. The requirements were elicited in cooperation with the pilot partners and responsible persons and the corresponding and adjacent work packages.

The scope of this deliverable is to present the system design of the CRISTAL DT. In preparation for this, two focal points were set in the preparation.

Firstly, the current state of the art in the field of IoT platforms and digital twins was compiled and briefly presented. On the one hand, this clarifies the context and area of application of the DT and the associated requirements and technical prerequisites and conditions. On the other hand, existing findings from other research projects can be included in the development.

Secondly, the requirements and technical prerequisites of the project partners of the pilots were collected. These specify the goals of the DT and its possible data processing functions. In addition, the design can be adapted to existing systems and their data models.

Based on this work, a system design of the DT was developed which enables the development of the DT within the task 5.3, useful for achieving the pilot goals.

1.1. Introduction

The overall objective of this project is to optimise the utilisation of inland waterway routes, and to improve the reliability by using planning strategies and technologies. As a central element, the inland waterway under consideration is to be mapped by a digital twin, and simulations and predictions are to be made possible with the data collected in this way.

Using a digital twin and the associated analysis methods, the aspect of robust long-term planning is to be addressed. To determine the specific direction of a digital Twin that serves this purpose, existing systems and infrastructure need to be understood. This includes current results in the area of IoT technologies,

platforms and services, as well as the status of the pilots in which the DT can be tested. These conditions are translated into concrete requirements for a twin and the associated software.

Based on the requirements identified, a concept for the architecture of the CRISTAL DT will be created. Interfaces and data flow mechanisms between the components, including sensors, platforms, external information systems and CRISTAL software components are also described.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 Alignment of D5.1 content to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

DELIVERABLE	Description in the GA	Respective chapters within this document	Explanation / Comment
D5.1 Technical concept of a digital twin	Based on the requirements identified the conceptual design of CRISTAL digital twin architecture will be built. Interfaces and data flow mechanisms between the components including sensors, platforms, external information systems and CRISTAL software components will also be specified in this deliverable.	<i>Chapter 7-15</i>	The requirements were described in an elevated manner and an architecture was created using the described methodology. In particular, the CRISTAL sensors and the project-specific output consumer SCMS were highlighted.
TASKS			
Task 5.1 Requirement Engineering, Architecture & System Design	This WP aims to elicit and formalize the stakeholder needs and priorities and to identify requirements related to the pilots. A state-of-the-art of the relevant technologies will be reviewed early in the project. The WP will later focus on specification of the requirements and design of the CRISTAL digital twin. The first step will define the scientific problem and analyses the functional and operational inland waterway requirements with respect to organizational dynamics, data governance and legal issues. Existing information systems, operational assets of end users will be analysed, and the results will be used as a base while elaborating the requirements. As a	<i>Chapter 1-6 (state-of-the-art)</i> <i>Chapter 7-15 (Requirement analysis and architecture)</i>	The first chapters provide a brief overview of relevant technologies from the field of IoT platforms as well as a classification of current definitions of digital twins. In addition, EU projects with a similar focus on digital twins are presented, and the usual form of reference architectures is described. Chapter 6 highlights aspects regarding software security that the digital twin must consider as a data-driven service.

	<p>result of this study, a Requirements Specification Document will be provided in accordance with IEEE Std. 29148:2011 (Systems and Software engineering- Life cycle processes – Requirement’s engineering). The Requirements Specification document will guide the project in all phases, specifically in the design phase. Based on the requirements identified in the first steps the conceptual design of the CRISTAL digital twin architecture will be built. A well-defined design process will be followed to ensure the production of a high-quality system that meets the needs of end-users by tracking identified requirements. During the design phase action planning and issue analysis techniques will be used to identify the pilot-independent and generic design features as well as pilot-specific constraints. Output of this task will be delivered in System Design Document</p>	<p>Chapter 7 onward describes the methodology for eliciting requirements. Chapter 10 onward describes the results of the elicitation and the individual use cases that the digital twin is to cover. This is followed by a description of a requirements catalogue and an architecture, which form the basis for the subsequent development.</p>
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1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The document is divided into two parts. The first part addresses state of the art technologies of IoT systems and digital twins. After the introduction an overview of the CRISTAL System is given. Based on this overview the position and responsibilities of the DT within this system can be adapted. Additionally, the first chapters provide an overview of the current state of IoT platforms and several communication protocols. Since the DT is to be integrated into such a system, this status is described in advance as a context. Afterwards, interoperability and data security will be discussed.

In the second part from chapter 7 onwards, the system design of the DT realised within the project is described. The use cases of the different pilots and their requirements will be stated out, as well as short descriptions of sensor components used within the CRISTAL project. The use cases will be described, and supplementary sequence diagrams and Mock-Ups can be found there as well. The requirements have been defined with the help of the methodology VOLERE and the prioritization methodology has been MoSCoW. Building upon this information the architecture of the DT(s) is defined and explained. Furthermore, some explanations and considerations about the software development are given.

2. Context of the technical environment

The DT is part of the CRISTAL System environment, an IoT platform system. This chapter introduces the DT into this environment to find a starting point for further research and decisions within the development.

2.1. CRISTAL System Overview

This section introduces a general overview of the CRISTAL systems and how the DT is classified. The overview picture shows how the data flow between the components is organised (see Figure 1). It therefore does not focus on the concrete implementation and usage of technologies and is not a comprehensive system architecture. But the connection between the individual components and developments in the work packages is presented. The graph given here represents a current status at the time of publication.

Figure 1: Overall Picture of the CRISTAL System Components

In the CRISTAL system, the DT is in the Knowledge Layer. As seen the main part of the data to be processed is collected by the pilots and passed on to the Synchro-Modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) and DT via a common data management system. Depending on the different cases, applications and pilots, the data in the DT is processed and prepared differently as the different pilots need different predictions to

match their needs. The recipients of this processed and prepared data are then the GUI of the DT, the SCMS or external systems (dashboards). The exact design and objectives of the pilots can be found in the respective deliverables of WP6-9. Relevant for the DT is the type of data that will be collected, and the data newly collected by the project through the CRISTAL sensor components.

As the DT will use, inter alia, machine learning to achieve the set objectives from the Grant Agreement, the available data is crucial for the development. Therefore, the whole design of the DT is built up from the analysis of the pilots, their data, and their needs. The possible output based on that, will be contextualised, and provided to the SCMS. This is a second step within the whole phase of design and development and will be influenced by the outcomes of the development after submission of this document. Therefore, the detailed analysis and decisions of this connection will be described within the documentation of development phase D5.3. An outlook will be given at the end, as well as the interfaces between the systems are considered within the architecture as well.

2.2. Reference Architecture IoT-A

Within the EU research project I2PANEMA, a detailed state-of-the-art analysis for the use of IoT technologies and sensor technology in the maritime space, especially of ports, was published (Joubert et al. 2020). We have used this publication as a starting point for our research, updated it accordingly and extended it with state-of-the-art research on digital twins and other relevant topics. As the previous overview of the CRISTAL System is a status of the current work at the time of submission and no final System Architecture of the overall CRISTAL System developed, a reference architecture for IoT platform is considered within this document. It was used to ensure the use of a DT in such a platform and to include already available knowledge and protocols in the later design development.

The concept of reference architecture (RA) refers to the layout of components and services and the best practices of an IT system that is implemented repeatedly with similar goals but different contexts, constraints, or business variants. An example of this would be the framework developed as a pattern with the intention of creating applications that share the same pattern, features, etc. According to this, development would focus more on IoT scenarios rather than applications (web, desktop, mobile) (Paul Fremantle 2015; Lea 2018).

It is important to note that an RA is more abstract than a classic system architecture, which was developed for a specific application with corresponding framework conditions and scenarios. (Bauer et al.).

It is true that an RA is more complex than a traditional architecture for the IoT due to the heterogeneity of concepts and technologies and the interaction of the different technologies used. It is relevant to understand the impact on, for example, scalability and other parts of the overall system when deciding on a particular design aspect. (This is one of the factors to consider in D5.1, System Design Document).

As the interoperability of several systems and the involvement of many different actors will be the most important challenge by developing the DT, this architecture will be shortly described to explain the context of the usage of the DT. Also, the project can be considered the foundation for all the EU efforts done in this area since then.

The book “Internet of Things for Architects” (Lea 2018) points out, that there are over 1.5 million different combinations of architectures to choose from (see also figure 2). In CRISTAL with different new sensors, technologies and systems must be dealt with, but they can be added to this landscape as well and stand for continuous further development in this field. In the next chapters there is more basic information and definitions for a better classification and understanding.

Figure 2 IoT Design Choices The full spectrum of various levels of IoT architecture from sensor to cloud and back (Lea 2018, pp. 26–38)

IoT-A (Cordis 2022) was a lighthouse EU-funded project (2010 - 2013) that established an Architectural Reference Model for the Internet of Things domain. In the project, common tools and approaches were developed to create a comprehensive reference architecture for IoT scenarios. It presents a series of characteristics that must be taken into consideration for the analysis of IoT architectures:

- **Architecture description.** Addresses the vision of architecture in relation to the project / product.
- **Model and distribution of information .** Addresses the problem of how information is treated and how it is distributed in the system.
- **Horizontality.** Ability to reuse the same blocks to provide different functionalities of the top layer.
- **Context knowledge and semantic capabilities.** Refers to the possibility of improving the information exchanged through semantic translators.
- **Technology specification and interoperability.** How much of the project / product depends on a particular technology and how to focus on interoperability.
- **Adaptation.** Capacity offered by the project / product regarding reactivity to environmental changes.
- **Programmability.** Defines APIs and specific standards for the development of an application.
- **Interface with the outside world.** Interfaces with which the end user interacts.
- **Work Plan.** Consideration of whether a product includes in its planning measures aimed at improving compatibility and / or development from the perspective of IoT.

- **Can the product interact with other articles?** Capacity or flexibility that a product presents when interacting with elements of the environment.
- **Obvious aspects of integration.** Evaluates whether a given product has taken into consideration basic aspects for integration into IoT architecture.

Additionally, a series of results was generated among which are the specifications of a reference architecture for the IoT. Through this RA, an understanding of an open architecture for the IoT has been created and it also addresses, among other things, issues of security and privacy as well as scalability and interoperability as a whole.

Besides research and private institutions, as it will be shown below, standardization bodies have done work in this domain. ITU has proposed a comprehensive reference model in IoT environment. Their contribution has been the recommendation ITU-T 2013 that clarifies the concept and scope of the IoT, identifying the fundamental characteristics and high-level requirements and describing the IoT reference model.

These are the functions of the different modules that compose the IoT’s functional model:

- **Security.** Among its responsibilities are Authorization, authentication, identity management.
- **Management.** It is responsible for: Configuration, State and Reporting.
- **IoT Process Management.** Responsible for: Process Modelling and Process Execution.
- **Service Organization.** Responsible for: Service Orchestration.
- **IoT Service.** Module responsible for: Registration of devices, historical data access, etc.
- **Virtual Entity.** It is responsible for handling the relations between the virtual entities (devices, sensors, etc.) and domain entities.
- **Communication.**

IoT-A introduces the concepts of views and perspectives. Its design is as follows and shown in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden**.³

Figure 3: IoT-A's views and perspectives (Torkaman and Seyyedi 2016, p. 156)

- **Views.** “Different angles for viewing an architecture that can be used when designing and implementing it” (Internet of Things - Architecture — IOT-A: Internet of Things Architecture 2021). The views include: Functional view, Information view, Deployment, and operation view, as seen in the image above.
- **Perspectives.** “Set of tasks, tactics, directives, and architectural decisions for ensuring that a given concrete system accomplishes one or more quality attributes”.

Based on these perspectives a holistic approach of software requirements is disposed. Those were considered also within the requirement analysis.

3. Digital Twin

In this chapter we will take a closer look at the architecture and the concept of a digital twin. The basic idea of a concept for digital twins is presented, thus creating a fundamental understanding of this complex of topics. Further definitions of different types of DTs are followed by a brief overview of EU research projects focusing on the development of a digital twin. Finally, there is an overview of architectural models.

3.1. Digital Twin Concept

The concept of a digital twin has not completely changed since 2002, especially when speaking about a physical adaption. In this case we are not talking about completely new concepts developed in the 2020s. Usually a digital twin is based on a digital information construct built on a physical system. It's the starting point and the base where this idea and concepts come from. It can be seen as a system itself and constructed as an entity on its own. Its parts remain connected throughout its life cycle and form "twins" in relation to each other.

Figure 4: Conceptual ideal for PLM (Grieves and Vickers 2017, p. 93)

Figure 4 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** shows the concept of a digital twin from a presentation by the Michigan University in 2002. The aim of the presentation was to form the Product Lifecycle Management Center. The digital twin consists of different elements, such as the virtual and the real space, as well as the connection for the data flow.

The digital twin is defined as an individual system with two components each. The first component is the physical component, which is inherently persistent. The second component is a new virtual component, which contains all the information of the physical system. Therefore, a mirroring of the system was realized from the virtual space to the real space and vice versa.

While going through the physical system's lifecycle, which can be separated into creation, production, operation and disposal, the virtual and real system remain connected. (Grieves and Vickers 2017, pp. 92–93)

The digital twin can for example reduce maintenance costs and provides a better overview of assets. The quality of data is improved which enables the optimization of day-to-day processes. The saved resources in combination with the improved lifecycle management allows a general servitization and business models

like product-as-a-service. In general, the benefits of a digital twin can be categorized into four categories, Analytical, Descriptive, Predictive and the Diagnostic Value.

The Analytical Value describes the provision of data that is usually hard to get, for example in dangerous or in physically inaccessible areas. The Descriptive Value describes the possibility to remotely view the assets information. The Predictive Value describes the ability of the Digital Twin to predict the future status of the asset based on gathered historical information. The Diagnostic Value describes how the Digital Twin can explain causal relations that led to the current state of the asset. (Moshood et al. 2021, pp. 16–17)

In addition, DTs are now being developed and used for a wide range of purposes. This starts with the incoming data to be processed, which often originate from different systems that are only marginally related to the system to be mapped. And it does not have to be explicitly a physical system in every case; it can also be a digital replica of a process. In this case, the influence and impact of a DT are slightly different, and the result often has to do with the visualisation of KPIs and information in the form of a dashboard. In the end, of course, the "form" of the data also influences the conception and processing, especially when it comes to real-time data and processing.

In the presented deliverable, most of the literature concerns digital twins (DT) with a product lifecycle. This is because early digital twin research was based on product lifecycle management (PLM) phases (Trauer et al. 2020). Not every digital twin concept in CRISTAL necessarily relates to a "product", but most of the architecture and design of a PLM DT can be applied to an infrastructure DT, nonetheless. As discussed before, there is no clear universal definition of a digital twin, which is why Naderi and Shojaei suggest using an interdisciplinary approach to researching digital twins. To better understand the role of DT in this project, a definition and its interpretation is discussed in the next section.

3.2. Definition of a Digital Twin

A definition that is consistent with a broad understanding of digital twins comes from Grieves and Vickers. They sum up their definition of a digital twin as follows:

Digital Twin (DT): "The Digital Twin is a set of virtual information constructs that fully describes a potential or actual physical manufactured product from the micro atomic level to the macro geometrical level. At its optimum, any information that could be obtained from inspecting a physical manufactured product can be obtained from its Digital Twin." (Grieves and Vickers 2017, p. 94)

Furthermore, Grievers and Vickers differentiate between two types of digital twins, Digital Twin Prototypes and Digital Twin Instances. They are used by the Digital Twin Environment for a variety of purposes.

Digital Twin Prototype (DTP): A Digital Twin Prototype contains information to describe and produce the physical version which duplicates the virtual version. It can include information requirements, a fully annotated 3D model, a bill of materials, a bill of processes, a bill of services, or a bill of disposal.

Digital Twin Instance (DTI): A Digital Twin Instance describes a physical object that the digital twin remains linked to. It can contain a fully annotated 3D model with Geometric Dimensioning and Tolerancing (GD&T) that describes the geometry of the physical instance and its components, a Bill of Materials that lists current components and all past components, a Bill of Process that lists the operations that were performed in creating this physical instance, along with the results of any measurements and tests on the instance, a

Service Record that describes past services performed and components replaced, and Operational States captured from actual sensor data, current, past actual, and future predicted.

Digital Twin Environment (DTE): A Digital Twin Environment is a multi-domain physics application space, where DTPs and/or DTIs can be used to predict and interrogate past, current, and future states of a digital twin. (Grieves and Vickers 2017, pp. 94–95)

As previously mentioned, this definition is also strongly oriented towards product lifecycles and is primarily designed for digital twins associated with machines or commodities. Since DT within CRISTAL is intended to cover infrastructure of waterways and parts of these themselves, a somewhat different interpretation of the definition must be found here. In the field of civil engineering, more and more digital twins are also being developed for existing infrastructure and natural systems such as cities or rivers. A detailed elaboration of a concept and workflow for such a development has been published by Pregnotato et al. They use the somewhat more general definition developed by the UK National Digital Twin Programme:

A digital twin is “a realistic digital representation of assets, processes and systems with a defining characteristic of a data connection between the real world and its digital representation”. (Pregnotato et al.)

Using this definition, it is clear the actual ideas of a DT also work outside of product lifecycles. Only the development and conception of such a DT differs significantly since other data sources and their interpretation are necessary. In addition, a connection between digital and physical twin is only possible on both sides to a limited extent. Among other things, in the case of this project, a controllable backward direction from the DT to the physical twins is not to be considered.

In the further course of the document, the workflow for development will be included. In the following section some EU projects are presented that have developed digital twins for infrastructure.

3.3. EU projects with focus on Digital Twin

The next chapters briefly present research projects from the near past that also dealt with the technology and concepts of a DT. These research projects had a different focus in detail than is the case in CRISTAL, but the consideration helps to classify them in the overall topic. Especially for the following steps of the development of a suitable architecture for the DT, a consideration of previous projects and experience is helpful and essential.

As those projects funded from the EU provide public information about their architecture and requirement analysis, that information will be used as base for the development of the architecture development of the CRISTAL DT. However, it was also noted that no consistent choice of architecture design was made. Therefore, the project documentation from SPHERE will be used primarily, as this was the best and most detailed described one (compare following section).

Iliad

The European Project **Iliad** (INTEGRATED Digital Framework FOR Comprehensive MARITIME DATA AND INFORMATION SERVICES) of the European Commission, funded under the Green Deal call for research proposals, develops virtual representations of the sea that will integrate earth observing, modelling and digital infrastructure to provide predictions of future developments “at sea” (European Commission 2022b). The project started in February 2022 and has a duration of 36 months, in which an extensive digital twin will be developed.

This digital twin aims to be data intensive and cost-effective by using different sources of data, like Earth Observation and advanced computing infrastructures (cloud computing, HPC, IoT, Big Data, social networks, etc.). A large amount of disparate data is brought together to enable communication with the system in the real world and allows the end user to explore the data in a fun and interactive way through geo virtualization or augmented virtual reality.

To share the data from the digital twin of the ocean and promote applications, an Iliad marketplace will be set up. (European Commission 2022b)

Digital Twin of the Ocean

Additionally, the European Commission is investing to develop a core **European Digital Twin Ocean**, which complements project, Iliad, to pilot the DTO concept. The European Digital Twin Ocean's ambition is to make ocean knowledge readily available to citizens, entrepreneurs, scientists, and policymakers by providing them with an innovative set of user-driven, interactive and visualization tools.

Leveraging on existing European science and assets, the European DTO will provide consistent high-resolution, multi-dimensional descriptions of the ocean. This includes its physical, chemical, biological, socio-ecological, and economical dimensions, with forecasting periods ranging from seasons to multi-decades (-> What is the European Digital Twin of the Ocean?). (European Commission 2022a)

SPHERE

SPHERE is a 4-year, Horizon 2020 project that aims to provide a BIM-based Digital Twin Platform to optimize the building lifecycle, reduce costs, and improve energy efficiency in residential buildings. A cloud-based collaborative Platform as a Service ICT Architecture will be developed, to link, capture and manage raw data produced by machines, systems, and products.

Stakeholders will interact with the platform through a dashboard where, depending on their rights and permissions based on their role with the real asset, they will have access to a different set of services and apps (European Commission).

DUET

The Horizon 2020 project **DUET** (Digital Urban European Twins for smarter decision making) started in 2019 and ended in November 2022. It's focused on a three-dimensional interface of city data for digital twin creation. City planners are able to manage resources, enhance development, reduce ecological footprints, and improve residential quality with the help of high-performance computer models and advanced cloud capabilities. (Duet 2022)

FEDeRATED

This initiative is an EU Member States driven project co-funded by the European Commission Connecting Europe Facility CEF. It focuses on interoperability between logistics platforms. However, a central focus within the initiative is the integration of digital twins. (FEDeRATED 2023)

The project has developed a master plan for this, tested it in small so-called living labs and evaluated it during its duration. The main issue this project faces is the missing possibility for trustfully and risk minimizing data sharing with other partners of a supply chain. The most data driven solutions for better operations planning or event-based alarm systems are depending on comprehensive data bases of physical goods, supply fleets or delivery corridors like railway nets though. Within the project the usage of digital twins collecting data about those physical entities were chosen to address this issue. Those should collect data from all relevant partners having information about the respective entity. Since these twins function like mirrors of the real entities, their data can also be used to simulate states of these entities in interaction with others or due to changes in external circumstances. (rudyhemeleers 2020)

This enables the previously mentioned functions of enterprises' interoperable platforms. The architectural structure of the data collection to ensure both security of the data and uniformity of processing was described in FEDeRATED Reference Data Sharing Architecture 2022.

3.4. Digital Twin Architecture

This chapter is bringing a definition and explanation of needed components to you as well as a link to an architecture of a digital twin designed within another research project.

Essential Components of a Digital Twin

Boyes and Watson 2022 concluded, that there is no concrete architecture for a digital twin, but there are certain concepts which all DT architectures should have in common. Table 2 shows six components that Boyes and Watson 2022 found useful.

Table 2 Definition of Components (Catapult 2021)

Live	the state information is available in a timeframe that is close enough to the underlying event
Digital coupling	the transmission mechanism between data source(s) and data consumption method(s) using a digital carrier medium
State	the particular condition the unique physical asset or process is in at a specific time
Physical asset or process	an entity with an existence that has economic, social or commercial value.
Virtual representation	an analogous description or logical model to its physical asset or process
Functional output	information transmitted to a system or human observer that is actionable to deliver value

Live means information must be promptly given to the DT, so it can operate on current data. The greater the delay between an event and the arrival of the events information the worse the digital twin and its subservices gets.

A **digital coupling** means virtual and physical parts of the digital twin are connected in a way that change in the virtual asset carries over to the physical asset and vice versa. The main aspect here is the connection and the bidirectional exchange.

A **state** stands for the point, that a digital twin contains information about its composition, attributes, and circumstances at a certain point in time. Of course, this is especially true for DT as an image of physical origins.

A digital twin represents a **physical asset** or **process** as mentioned before. Both variants are different in their expression and representation and are handled differently, but the two head categories are still very well suited for a rough classification.

A digital twin inherently translates this **asset** into the virtual space. A digital twin transfers this value into virtual space. The important aspect here is the virtual equivalent and generation of added value, which becomes visible and transferable.

Speaking about **functional output** means, that there is value to the information gain of a digital twin, which is used by other services. When talking about functional output, it means that the information gain of a digital twin that is used by other services has value. What is more, it means that the output created becomes usable and can be used, for example, for better assessments, evaluations, and further developments.

Without any of these six components the corresponding architecture does not describe a digital twin. At least one of these requirements must therefore be fulfilled to be considered an architecture for a digital twin and the explanations basically not only describe the "necessary" conditions for an architecture, but also provide a further definition for a digital twin.

A common approach to incorporate these aspects into an architecture is a layer model. A variety of layer models exists, each featuring a different interpretation of what comprises an architecture (Boyes and Watson 2022, p. 4). Boyes and Watson 2022 list a few examples of the use of this approach for digital twins:

- a 3-layer architecture comprising physical controls, cyber-physical synchronization, and a cyber model (Leng et al. 2020)
- a 3-layer architecture (data visualization, data processing and a semantic layer) with an optional data acquisition layer. The semantic 'layer' located parallel to the visualization and processing layers, providing the overall system model and data integration (Haße et al.)
- a 3-layer model consisting of four parts: three layers (physical, digital, and cyber) and communication for data exchange among the three layers (Aheleroff et al. 2021)
- a 4-layer model comprising the physical layer, data extraction and consolidation layer, cyberspace layer and the interaction layer (Zheng and Sivabalan 2020)
- a 5-layer model comprising a virtual component motion joint level, component/device logic level, production line logic level, data aggregation/scene logic level, and digital twin information (Fan et al. 2021)
- a 5-layer model comprising data acquisition layer, transmission layer, digital modelling layer, model integration layer and services layer (Lu et al. 2020)
- a 6-layer model adapting a 5-level CPS architecture (Lee et al. 2015) the layers comprise physical devices, data acquisition, local data repositories, IoT gateway, cloud-based information repositories, and an emulation and simulation layer (Redelinghuys et al. 2020)
- a 6-layer model comprising the following layers: physical, ingestion, persistence, inference, service and consumption (Mostafa et al. 2021)

While there is no concise definition of a digital twin architecture, it might be helpful to look at some concrete implementations of digital twins in other literature or projects as well. Either way, the selection of a suitable architecture for a digital twin depends in particular on the requirements and the use in practice and is based on the analyses of the use cases. Therefore, the architecture provided within the EU project SPHERE will be shortly described within the next section. The design decisions made were also considered as start for our own architecture design of the DT.

Sphere – Architecture

As previously described in chapter 3.2 the SPHERE project has developed a well-documented digital twin, which is similar in scope and design to the technologies being developed for CRISTAL. For those reasons we will take a detailed look at the architecture and development of SPHEREs Digital Twin ecosystem.

Figure 5 shows the architecture of the third draft of the developed digital twin ecosystem. It's important to emphasize that SPHERE highlights its cloud-based collaborative platform aspect with many connected services and hides its actual digital twin behind the SPHERE API, as seen in SPHERE Data. Nevertheless,

some of these platform related aspects are important for digital twins and CRISTAL, as specific solutions to data linking and managing might also apply there.

Figure 5: Third draft for the SPHERE architecture (European Commission 2020, p.44)

The SPHERE architecture is focused on being detachable and modular, to serve multiple pilots and their distinct set of services. To implement this the following separation was made.

There are components which are shared across all pilots, like the user interface, security (SPHERE Shared components) and data separation on the platform (SPHERE Data). On the other hand, there are components which are specific to each pilot, e.g., pilot services (SPHERE Services), sensor data integration (External Data) and external applications, tools or platforms which provide or use specific data of the pilot.

While each pilot has several tools to process the digital twin’s data, these can be placed in only a few categories (Performance Tool, Design Tool, Maintenance Tool, etc.) which are valid for all pilots.

Each category has its own demands pertaining the digital twin’s data, which consists of the asset and geometry data, in this case hosted by the Neanex portal (NEXT) platform, and the sensor and file data, hosted by the Refurbify and Virtual Construction Management Platform, VCMP (VRM), which is also connected to the Database Management System.

The direction of the data flow between each component is shown as arrows and allows the preliminary designing of tool agnostic interfaces from the digital twin to the individual tool categories.

In the later chapter 14 of the architecture for the DT, we take up these previous explanations and findings again and apply them to the requirements in CRISTAL accordingly. The approach described in the previous chapters then serves the specification and forms the basis, among other things.

4. IoT Communication

As described in the previous chapters, data acquisition and handling are very important responsibilities of IoT systems. Especially the usage of digital services, new sensor technologies as used in CRISTAL and digital twins increase their importance. A detailed overview of the relevant communication technologies for the whole project CRISTAL will be given within D5.2 Data integration and data model. Therefore, here a brief overview about relevant concepts for the DT is given. An initial overview was collected from Joubert et al. This overview was evaluated, shortened on the relevant topics, and complemented.

4.1. IoT Protocol Stack

The field of IoT communication now offers a wide range of (standard) protocols that have become established in the past. The IoT stack, shown in Figure 6, gives a brief overview of the technologies which are relevant for a communication. At the application layer, two of the most commonly used protocols are the Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) and the Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP). or devices with limited resources, there is an extension called MQTT for Sensor Networks (MQTT-SN). Further application layer protocols are HTTP, DDS, AMQP and XMPP. All these protocols rely on either TCP or UDP using IPv4 and IPv6. Generally, security is built on top of the transport layer. Depending on the use of TCP and UDP, Transport Layer Security (TLS) or Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS) is applied. In general, IoT communication is based on wireless networking technologies, such as Wi-Fi, 4G/5G, LPWANs like LoRaWAN and NB-IoT or Bluetooth. In some cases, wired technologies like Ethernet are also used. With respect to real time requirements Time Sensitive Networking (TSN) can be an option as well.

Figure 6: I2PANEMA IoT Protocol Stack (Joubert et al. 2020)

4.2. Application Layer Protocols

Application layer protocols define how data is exchanged via TCP or UDP transport, for example in terms of data format, message types and reliability. In the IoT, the protocols must meet certain requirements, e.g., in terms of bandwidth, energy consumption and computing power. Another crucial factor is the communication pattern.

Classic World Wide Web communication is based on a pure client/server model. Here, communication takes place according to the request/response principle with a one-to-one connection. Although this

approach is applicable to many IoT use cases, it has some disadvantages. First, clients need to poll data regularly, which increases resource consumption (energy, computing power and bandwidth). Second, one-to-many or many-to-many communication is not possible, which is important for IoT communication where thousands of sensors send data to multiple servers simultaneously. Furthermore, communication in this approach is inherently synchronous and does not allow decoupling of devices.

Another approach that has gained acceptance is publish/subscribe. This addresses exactly these problems. It involves publishing data to a single device or a group of devices in an event-based manner. Regardless of how Publish/Subscribe is implemented, e.g., with or without a broker, it eliminates the problems of polling and being limited to one-to-one communication. Furthermore, in most implementations, communication is managed by a central instance, decoupling the devices. However, this also results in this instance being a single point of failure, which is a major disadvantage.

Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT)

MQTT is one of the most widely used application layer protocols in IoT. It is a lightweight M2M protocol based on a broker-based publish/subscribe approach (see Figure 7). A publisher can publish data on a topic or group of topics. For a subscriber who can subscribe to topics, they serve as a kind of content filter. Topics are strings consisting of one or more topic levels separated by slashes. MQTT supports single-level (+) and multi-level (#) placeholders to publish to multiple topics simultaneously by replacing either one or more topic levels. A subscriber is notified each time data is published in the topics to which they are subscribed. In this approach, the broker is responsible for distributing the messages, managing the subscribers and storing the messages. Since there is no direct connection between publisher and subscriber, communication is decoupled in terms of space, time and synchronisation. Publisher and subscriber therefore do not have to be known to each other, i.e. address, port etc. are unknown. This means that they do not have to run simultaneously and can communicate asynchronously.

Figure 7: MQTT – Broker-based Publish/Subscribe (The HiveMQ Team 2023)

MQTT is based on TCP, and it supports TLS for security, including authentication and encryption mechanisms. MQTT provides three qualities of service (QoS) levels. The first level (0) doesn't give any guarantees, that means the message is delivered at most once (fire and forget). The second level (1) ensures that the message is delivered at least once. That means the sender waits for message delivery to be acknowledged. Here, the message can potentially be transmitted more than once. For the highest QoS level (2), the message is delivered exactly once by using a four-step handshake. The higher the QoS level, the higher the reliability will be. However, the communication overhead increases as well. MQTT also

supports persistent sessions, message queuing and retained messages (MQTT Essentials - All Core Concepts explained 2022). Last will and Testament (LWT) messages can be used by clients to leave a message at the broker to still respond after disconnection. LWT messages are sent during the connection process with the broker. MQTT supports WebSocket communication, which enables the use of MQTT in a web browser.

MQTT for Sensor Networks (MQTT-SN) is an extension of MQTT developed for the use in resource constrained environments. IoT devices are usually limited in bandwidth, energy consumption, CPU, and memory. Thus, MQTT-SN is optimized to meet these constraints. The main differences, compared to MQTT, are (MQTT - The Standard for IoT Messaging 2022):

- Usage of UDP instead of TCP
- Smaller message sizes
- Smaller topic id, pre-defined topics, and shorter topic names
- Gateway discovery
- Client sleep mode
- QoS level -1

As shown in Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. 8, there are two different ways to integrate MQTT-SN into MQTT. Both ways require an MQTT-SN to MQTT gateway. In the first way, an external gateway is used to translate MQTT-SN messages into MQTT-compliant messages. The other method uses a gateway that is directly integrated into the broker. A distinction is also made between two types of gateways. A transparent gateway uses one MQTT connection for each MQTT SN client. An aggregating gateway, on the other hand, uses a single connection between gateway and broker. If a client is not in the gateway's network, an MQTT-SN forwarder can be used, which merely forwards the MQTT-SN

packets without changing them.

Figure 8: Integration of MQTT-SN using Gateways (Joubert et al. 2020b)

WebSocket

The WebSocket protocol (RFC 6455) standardised by the IETF was developed for bidirectional communication between web applications (client) and web servers (server). Periodic queries and multiple connections on the client side should thus be avoided. Instead, a client opens a single and permanent connection to the server via TCP. The communication takes place in two steps. In the first step, the client establishes the connection to the server via a handshake. In the second step, if the handshake process was

successful, both can communicate bidirectionally. Since the communication is based on TCP, security can be provided by means of TLS.

5. IoT Interoperability

The **IEEE (IEEE 2022)** defines interoperability as the ability of two or more systems or components to exchange information and use the information exchanged. Within the project, a very large number of different data sources from different sensors and systems and with different levels of security requirements for the DT must be considered. Therefore, the interoperability of the DT and the system in which it is to be used must be particularly ensured.

Since there are several types of sources that provide different data in different formats, it can be helpful to provide a standard view for each type of data so that they can be imported and exported to the data management system in the same way. The benefits of a high degree of interoperability are:

- Lower costs associated with interoperable systems, as fewer resources and additional maintenance are required.
- Access to information can be granted to all relevant stakeholders.
- Quality of data is improved as more sources can be brought together.
- Minimizes the time required data processing and thus increases organisational efficiency.

Within the following sections the SSN Ontology as description for sensor observations and sampling activities as well as the River Information System (RIS), an interoperability project for inland navigation traffic and transport management, are described.

5.1. SSN Ontology

To describe sensors, actuators, samplers, their observations, actuation, and sampling activities, World Wide Web Consortium (W3C (World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) 2022)) and Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC 2022) partial Data on the Web (SDW) working group developed a set of ontologies which includes a lightweight core module called SOSA (<https://www.w3.org/ns/sosa>) and an extension module called Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) (<https://www.w3.org/ns/ssn>). (Bauer et al.) That information was initially collected from Joubert et al.

The SSN has a horizontal and vertical modularization architecture as shown in Figure 9. It includes SOSA (Sensor, Observation, Sample and Actuator) for its fundamental classes and properties. SSN and SOSA can support a wide range of applications and use cases from large-scale scientific monitoring to industrial and private infrastructures, ontology engineering and the Web of Things.

Figure 9 The SOSA and SSN ontologies and their vertical and horizontal modules (<https://www.w3.org/ns/ssn>)

Sensors, their capabilities, observations, and methods can be described by the SSN ontology. The ontology contains parts of the specification for sensors, as well as concepts for operation and survival domains. The operation time and acquisition purpose of the deployed macro instrument are explained by a structure for field distributions. Related but non-sensor specific specifications such as units of measurement, locations, hierarchies of sensor types, and feature and property hierarchies have been excluded from the ontology. An example can be found in Figure 10. External ontologies can also be linked to the definitions via subclass or equivalence relationships. (Compton et al. 2012)

Figure 10 The SSN ontology, key concepts, and relations, split by conceptual modules. (Compton et al. 2012, p. 27)

5.2. River Information System (RIS)

The European Committee for Drawing up Standards in the field of Inland Navigation (CESNI) was established by the European Commission in 2015. This committee deals with technical standards that are to be observed at international and European level to ensure the interoperability of various inland navigation systems. The aim is that European and international regulations can refer to these technical standards. The task of CESNI is to advise on the uniform interpretation and realisation of the technical standards, the method of interpreting the standards and the exchange of information and monitoring mechanisms between the Member States. Other topics in which CESNI provides expertise are technical requirements for specific vehicles, maritime safety and environmental protection. (CESNI - Comité Européen pour l'Élaboration de Standards dans le domaine de la Navigation Intérieure 2021)

The concept of River Information Services (RIS) (CESNI 2023) deals with information services in inland navigation support traffic and transport management, including interfaces with other transport modes. In this context, Directive 2005/44/EC on harmonised river information services on inland waterways in the EU was adopted. The RIS Directive is based on technical and operational standards and refers to the following four key technologies: Electronic Chart Display and Information System (Inland ECDIS), Notices to Skippers (Nts), Automatic Identification System (AIS) and Electronic Reporting International (ERI).

The European River Information Services System (EuRIS), as a central platform of national RIS systems, contains an implementation of the named key technologies and implements the standards set by CESNI. EuRIS as European platform thus fulfils the objective of processing and summarising large amounts of information and making it available for stakeholders. (Zwicklhuber and Kaufmann)

Figure 11: System architecture of EuRIS (Zwickhuber and Kaufmann)

The standardisation and its harmonisation shall contribute to the achievement of the RIS objectives by:

- Increasing safety in inland ports and rivers,
- Improving the efficiency of inland navigation - Optimising the resource management of the waterborne transport chain through information exchange,
- Better and more efficient use of inland waterway infrastructure - providing information on the state of the fairways,
- Environmental protection - providing traffic and transport information for an efficient disaster response process,
- Better integration of inland navigation in multimodal supply chains by providing accurate and timely information to support traffic management.

The system architecture can be found in Figure 11. Services considered in RIS are:

- Fairway information services for planning, execution, and monitoring of voyages (e.g., water levels, opening hours of locks, etc.),
- Traffic information services on vessel positions for tactical and strategic planning,
- Traffic management to optimise the use of infrastructure (incl. estimated arrival times),
- Accident response services (CAS) for registering vessels and forwarding important data to rescue teams in case of emergency,
- Cargo and fleet management,
- Statistical and customs services for data collection,
- Automated transfer of voyage data to calculate charges and initiate invoicing procedures.

For the CRISTAL system, these specifications may become relevant as soon as they are to be included in the pilots. In addition, connections to other systems must be discussed, as certain specifications for data exchange must be observed here. Within chapter 13 the data collection from external services is considered within the requirements. A more detailed description of the affection of the DT will be contained within D5.2.

6. Security

The security layer of an DT architecture will be a vertical layer to ensure adequate and controlled access to the platform's data and operations. Much of the data collected by sensors or external systems require restricted access (e.g., information about the goods a ship carries may be confidential for business reasons). The proliferation of "Connected Things" driven by the IoT has prompted the need for "Secure Things" that are critical in preventing the sophisticated system attacks. And the reasons that apply to this, as well as generally valid reasons in software development for IT security, can of course also be transferred and applied to the development of digital twins. Given the security vulnerabilities of e.g., Use Cases, the owners could be primarily concerned about the following (Archiveddocs 2009):

- Overall: How can we secure our "software"?
- Overall: What damage can potential attackers do?
- Specific: How can an attacker change the authentication data?
- Specific: What is the impact if an attacker can read the user profile data?
- Specific: What happens if access is denied to the user profile database?

There are different categories and levels of detail of the different questions, as well as the two basic overarching directions "How can something be secured?" and "What damage can be done?". Taken together, this helps to ensure that stakeholders think about the issue of security, that possible vulnerabilities are revealed and, furthermore, that they are made transparent. In addition to the right choice of technologies, predefined processes, such as STRIDE and DREAD analysis, can also help. In the process of selecting helpful technologies in this context, one can also orient oneself well on methodologies and experiences in the area of IoT systems. In the following chapter, some points are listed as examples. Nevertheless, security should be an integral part of the system design from the beginning (security by design).

6.1. STRIDE and DREAD Analysis

A typical security analysis of IT solution encompasses detailed description of the assets (i.e., what needs to be protected? What is its value), stakeholders (their roles and rights), possible threat scenarios (attack vectors and inherent vulnerabilities) followed by standard security countermeasures. For doing security analysis for IT solution, Microsoft's STRIDE methodology is an option. STRIDE is an abbreviation that stands for Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information disclosure, Denial of service and Elevation of privileges which are type of security threats described briefly in the table below.

Table 3 STRIDE threat description (Jegeib 2023)

Spoofing	Authentication	Pretending to be something or someone other than yourself
Tampering	Integrity	Modifying something on disk, on a network or in a memory
Repudiation	Non-repudiation	Claiming that you didn't do something, or where not responsible
Information disclosure	Confidentiality	Providing information to someone not authorized to see it: data leak or privacy breach
Denial of service	Availability	Absorbing resources needed to provide service
Elevation of privilege	Authorization	Allowing someone to do something they're not authorized to do

When the weaknesses have been identified after this analysis, it is necessary to carry out an assessment. The effects can be totally different, e.g., only a few users or all users are affected, and the exploitation of the vulnerability can also be evaluated from very simple to very difficult. In addition, of course, there is the classic aspect of critical impact. Is it just an advertisement and nothing much happens, or do dangers arise, for example, as described in the example above? These individual assessments lead to an overall evaluation and provide a prioritisation and assessment of the existing vulnerabilities and dangers. This analysis is called DREAD. DREAD has five categories and the abbreviation stand for:

Table 4 DREAD analysis categories

Damage	How much damage could the attack cause?
Reproducibility	How easy is it to reproduce the attack?
Exploitability	How much work is it to launch the attack?
Affected users	How many people will be impacted?
Discoverability	How easy is it to discover the threat?

Each category is weighted and the total score per case then provides a prioritisation and assessment of severity. Beyond that, the decisive step follows, namely the considerations and execution regarding a reduction of the attack potential, i.e., if possible, a prevention or avoidance of damage.

To give an example. If e.g., information from the DT is provided to the SCMS and this leads to ships being stopped, then that would be a big problem for various reasons and ways of looking at things. Many people would have a problem then and it could have a big impact. What must be guaranteed at the point

is that the associated transmitted data has not been manipulated. Therefore, it is necessary to think about possible entry points as a first step and of course then think about a mitigation.

6.2. Keycloak

To ensure the safety as described in the previous chapter for the CRISTAL project the applications must be secured as well as the connection to the server.

In WP5 there will be an API developed for the DT, as well as potentially the Data Visualisation in the frontend, which need authentication and authorization to prevent unauthorised users access to data worthy of protection. Furthermore, the backend with the database and the REST interface must be secured. The authorization allows to grant access only to the specific pilots. Especially the connection to the Keycloak server as to the frontend and backend should be encrypted which will be described in the next chapter, called Traefik. This ensures that the credentials are protected. (Das and Samdaria 2014, p. 72)

These requirements create the need for an access management tool such as Keycloak, which is an Open-Source authentication service for securing applications and services. It supports features like Single-Sign On (SSO), Identity Brokering and Social Login as well as User Federation. Keycloak uses standard protocols such as OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0 and SAML (Keycloak 2023). Keycloak has already found adopters in commercial, government and research applicators (GitHub 2023).

An example of an application request is shown Figure 12.

Figure 12: The authorization code flow (iLeri 2021)

6.3. Traefik

The server will be secured by HTTPS to ensure a secure connection and to prevent attacks on the credentials for example. To implement this in this project Traefik could be a solution and the consequences are explained below using the example. Traefik is an open-source edge router that helps facilitate service publishing. The router receives requests for the Keycloak server as well as for the backend and frontend and forwards them automatically. Furthermore, Traefik supports HTTPS and TLS which secures the server connection. (Traefik.io 2023)

Figure 13 Traefik and the services (Rescorla 2018)

Figure 13 shows an example of the functionality of the Traefik and the routing between the services. Traefik forwards request for the services and they can be reached under different URLs. Each individual service is accessible and secured via HTTPS.

7. Digital Twin System Design Guidelines

Based on the state-of-the-art analysis made in the previous chapters, several design decisions and the development of the CRISTAL DT must be done. The decision-making process is based on the following principles of software development.

7.1. System Development

The process of system development can be divided into the following phases:

- **Planning:** As typically for any project beginning, the planning is made here. Execution times, responsibilities and different tasks are determined and recorded as for example via Gantt diagram.
- **Analysis:** During this process facts, possible risks and problems are collected. A system analysis studies this as a whole and/or decomposed. Thus, the objectives of it are identified as well as needed functionalities.
- **Design:** In next section this point will be described in more detail.
- **Deployment:** This process is responsible for the execution of the project planning. It does not end until the project is delivered.
- **Maintenance:** After delivery of the project this phase starts. During it maintenance of the project outcome, fixing bugs and smaller developments of evolutionary functionalities are made. To manage those, maintenance tools for monitoring the application and error detection are recommended.

The planning was initially done within the Grant Agreement before project start (Grant Agreement-101069838-CRISTAL 2022). The analysis of several IoT technologies and concepts was shortly described within the first part of this document. It was also essential to acquire current results in the field of development and use of digital twins in existing infrastructure. Accordingly, it remains open to elaborate specific requirements of the project pilots and realise the design and the deployment. Those parts are the outcome of the analysis phase of the CRISTAL DT.

The design guidelines are described in the coming section. Afterwards, the requirements and the designed architecture are written down. The deployment will be evaluated within the deliverable D5.3. Maintenance would happen afterwards, which why it is not included within the projects scope.

As previously mentioned within section 3.1 by Pregolato et. al. evaluated a workflow especially for development of digital twins and considered special risks and needed working steps. The three phases of system development which will be done during this project (Analysis, Design and Development) can be concretized by this workflow to get a better understanding of those and the work which needs to be done. The workflow includes the following steps:

- **Data and need acquisition:** Collecting information about operational processes to identify objectives and decisions the DT should support and actions to provide feedback between DT and infrastructure.
- **Digital modelling:** Creation of a 'virtual' model which can visualize, simulate, model, or control the behaviour of the structure.
- **Sensor data transmission:** Selection, connection, and use of appropriate sensors to support the virtual model.

- **Data / Model integration:** Integration of the DT into the real world to make the outcome usable, as well as a connection between real and virtual twin creates the value of a DT.
- **Operation:** Deployment as well as performance improvement.

The first point refers to the analysis phase. Based on that the following three points clarify the steps of the design and development phase. The last point corresponds to the deployment as described above and will be detailed written down in D5.3. The methodologies used to fulfil this workflow phases of analysis and design are written down within the next chapters.

7.2. System Design Process

The process of system design describes how a new IT solution or a replacement of existing systems or their components will be developed to meet new requirements. System architecture, interfaces as well as system data management are directly affected by design decisions.

The design enables the concepts and business ideas to be captured and translated into IT processes. It is therefore an essential element. Therefore, the processes affected by the designed system must be well understood, including existing infrastructure, the hardware and software components used, the communication channels and the storage locations and addresses for the system data required and used.

Developing a system pursues the aim of a reliable, effective, and maintainable system as possible, while all during analysis specified requirements are meet. Thus, the creation of a system design always deals with a trade-off between different objectives. Especially in distributed systems, it is almost impossible to achieve the maximum possible results out of these objectives. This is intended to create systems that are consistent as well as available and resilient. (Brewer 2012)

The direct involvement of all interested parties (in CRISTAL all three pilots and the SCMS) in the analysis phase is therefore of great importance. Afterwards, a system based on the collected requirements will be designed accordingly to the design guidelines and is written down within chapters 14 and 15. A detailed documentation of the DT and the development decisions will be written down within D5.3.

7.3. CRISTAL Design Guidelines

The software engineering process Rational Unified Process (RUP) (Wikipedia 2023) is used to handle the design tasks in the CRISTAL project related to the Digital Twin. The goal of RUP is a framework for development of high-quality software meeting requirements while schedule and budget keep predictable, specified in CRISTAL by the available person-months. Therefore, RUP provides an approach for assigning tasks and responsibilities. As guidelines, templates and tool mentors are provided for each team member without high access barrier, the productivity of teams can be increased.

The Rational Unified Process is composed of the following workflows (Joubert et al. 2020):

- Business Modelling Workflow: The main purpose of this workflow is to understand the structure and dynamics of the organization.
- Requirements Workflow: The Requirement Workflow is for:
 - Coming to an agreement with the users on what the system should do

- Giving system developers a better understanding of the requirements on the system
- Providing a basis for planning the technical contents of iterations
- Analysis & Design Workflow: In this workflow, the requirements are transformed into a design of the system to-be and a robust architecture is evolved for the system.
- Implementation Workflow: In this workflow, the classes and objects are implemented in terms of components, and the results produced by the individual implementers are integrated.
- Test Workflow: As its name implies, the system is tested throughout this workflow.
- Project Management Workflow: This workflow provides a framework for managing software projects and managing risks.
- Configuration and Change Management Workflow: This workflow provides an audit trail on why, when and by whom any artefact was changed.
- Environment Workflow: This workflow enables the users to adapt and tailor the Rational Unified Process to suit the needs of an organization or project. (Joubert et al. 2020a)

The design task of the CRISTAL project is based on the Analysis & Design Workflow process (see figure below). The following steps are adapted accordingly throughout the design task of the project:

1. Use-Case Analysis
2. Architectural Design
3. Use-Case Design (mainly defined in WP6)
4. Class Design (in parts)

The steps 1-3 will be described within the chapters 11, 14 and 15, considering the definition of requirements listed within the chapter 13.

Figure 14: Steps of the Analysis and Design Workflow (Joubert et al. 2020a)

8. Technical Requirement Analysis

The following section defines the scientific problem and analyse the functional and operational requirements with respect to organizational dynamics, human factors, and legal issues. The Stakeholder Requirements and Business Scenarios out of WP1, e.g., as described in the deliverables “D1.1 - Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements” and “D1.2 - Stakeholders Evaluation and Key Innovative Technology Assessment”, form a starting point for the requirements analysis.

This part is in accordance with IEEE Std. 29148:2011 (Systems and Software engineering- Life cycle processes – Requirements engineering). The Requirements Specification will guide the project through the phases, especially the design and development phase.

The aim of the requirements analysis within the CRISTAL project is the collection and grouping of the requirements mainly from the pilots and for the SCMS.

8.1. Scope of the Requirement Analysis

The IEEE Std 610.12-1990 standard defines a requirement as a condition or capability that a system must meet in order to satisfy a stakeholder need or to fulfil an objective, contract, or specification. Accordingly, the term requirements analysis refers to the process of deriving and refining requirements. In addition to functional objectives, requirements may also describe operational conditions and how the substantive objectives are to be achieved. Furthermore, end-user needs, laws, guidelines, and regulations (such as security aspects) require additional requirements that cannot be derived from the KPIs.

8.2. Requirement Analysis in the CRISTAL project

In the case of the CRISTAL project, the KPIs of task T1.2 from WP1 provide a first definition of the objectives. The KPIs defined in WP1 could limit their view to the operating result. Therefore, we have asked the stakeholders of the pilots to provide requirements to obtain a common understanding of the further objectives and expectations in the scenarios that are not covered by the requirements derived from the KPIs.

These requirements are fundamental for WP5, especially task T5.3 “Smart Inland Waterway Monitor”, the implementation of the DTs and for other (technical) work packages (like WP2, WP3, WP6, WP7, WP8 and WP9). Furthermore, the validation in WP10 could also be based on this document.

9. Methodology and Definition for Requirements

This chapter describes the methodology of the requirements analysis.

9.1. Methodology selection

A large number of different methods for requirements analysis exists, which vary greatly in scope and focus. Two main goals for the CRISTAL project are: Results should be concrete implementations of DTs for the scenarios of the pilots as well as a generally valid reference architecture for the DT. Since at the beginning of the project many requirements regarding the DT were unclear and partly unspecific and there were many different views regarding the functionalities, we looked for a methodology to guide through requirements analysis that met the two essential criteria: to define a process for how requirements should be collected and a framework for a structured documentation.

Methodologies need to be characterized by criteria (Birk). To this end, the authors establish a set of common criteria and define the concept of landscape as a space with features as dimensions. Figure 15 as shown below, visualize the landscape defined by those two criteria. According to that landscape, there are two candidates which seem to fit better: ReqMan and VOLERE (see <https://www.volere.org/>).

Figure 15: Landscape of the criteria artefact orientation (horizontal axis) and process orientation (vertical axis) [taken from Birk08]

The quality and reuse-oriented requirements management - ReqMan was developed in 2006 as a requirement analysis methodology especially designed for small and mid-size enterprises (SMEs) (Ehresmann et al. 2006). The aim of the framework is to improve existing structures and increase their process quality. Furthermore, the framework is implemented in various tools to support requirements engineering for SMEs. In doing so, the framework focuses almost exclusively on processes and technology components and focuses its view on MEs and is not suitable for more complex cross-company scenarios.

For the design of a reference architecture for DT, a framework is sought and needed that is suitable for analysing and mapping those scenarios. Therefore, VOLERE seems to be more suitable than ReqMan as a requirements analysis methodology for CRISTAL. The following section describes the VOLERE methodology and our extension for the CRISTAL project more detailed.

9.2. Methodology description

VOLERE covers the discovery, communication, and management of requirements for any type of system (software, hardware, services, and goods) or anything else to develop. The method can work with any type of development method: agile and sequential and also with most requirements tools (e.g., Jira). VOLERE suggests a series of steps to follow:

1. Define the purpose and scope of the project.
2. Stakeholder identification and analysis.
3. Business Use Cases.
4. Scenarios.
5. Writing the requirements: functional and non-functional.
6. Validation of requirements.
7. Communicating the requirements.

9.3. VOLERE enhancement for CRISTAL

One goal of the CRISTAL project is to develop a digital twin usable for three pilots. Because of that, we have extended the VOLERE methodology with two additional steps.

In the first additional step, we have identified which requirements occurs in more than one case. Chapters 11 and 12 documents the outcome of this step regarding to the requirements. An architecture framework should consider these requirements.

In the second additional step, we grouped the requirements and prioritized them. Chapter 13 documents the result of this step in a tabular overview.

These requirement groups (mainly for the pilots) provide a condensed view of the core objectives that the architectural framework should consider. In addition, the prioritization of the groups provides the foundation for design decisions in the process of creating the architectural framework.

9.4. Requirements

There are several definitions of a requirement. One of them is given by the ISO:

“A requirement is Statement that identifies a product (includes product, service or enterprise) or process operational, functional or design characteristic or constraint, which is unambiguous, testable or measurable, and necessary for product or process acceptability”. (ISO 9795172)

Requirements classification

The VOLERE methodology establishes a classification of requirements into the following different groups (Robertson and Robertson 2017):

- Functional requirements
- Non-functional requirements
- Project constraints identify the interaction of the project with its environment.
- Project drivers are favour factors that drive the project. For example, the purpose of the specific Digital Twin is a driver of the development.
- Project issues are the set of conditions under which the development of the project will be carried out.

The requirements workflow usually consists of the following steps as shown in Figure 16:

1. **Identify** sources of requirements. Own knowledge, stakeholders, regulation, standards, etc.
2. **Capture** the requirements.
3. **Define** a detailed requirements specification following a requirements template (see chapter 13).
4. **Analyse** and assess the requirements obtained for each pilot site.
5. **Adjust** requirements to integrate feedbacks and suggestions provided by different stakeholders for each pilot use cases defined in CRISTAL.

Figure 16: Requirements workflow

Functional Requirements

VOLERE methodology defines functional requirements as the basic subject matter of the system: an action that the product must be able to perform and something that the product must do. VOLERE divides them into the following two groups:

- Functional requirements
- Data requirements

Non-Functional requirements

The VOLERE methodology defines non-functional requirements as the behavioural properties that the specified functions must have (performance, usability).

- Look and feel
- Usability
- Performance
- Operational
- Maintainability and Support
- Security
- Audit requirements
- Cultural and political
- Legal

Requirement template in CRISTAL

The methodology creates a template with the approach of facilitating the definition of requirements by identifying all aspects as quickly as possible. The following figure 17 from the VOLERE web illustrates this.

Figure 17: Robertson 2012 - Volere Requirement Specification Template Robertson (2012)

One of the possibilities for Priorisation is to use MoSCoW prioritisation methodology (Project Smart 2023; Wikipedia 2022). MoSCoW was developed by Dai Clegg of Oracle UK in 1994.

The technique is used in management, business analysis, project management and software development to achieve a common understanding of the importance they attach to meeting each requirement.

The term MoSCoW is an acronym derived from the first letter of each of the four categories (Must have, Should have, Could have and Won't have):

- **Must have:** The requirements marked as must have to be included in the development for the project to be successful. If even one must requirement is missing, the project delivery should be considered a failure. It is useful to be clear about this before the project starts (as far as possible), as this is the minimum scope for the product to be considered useful. Can also be considered as an acronym for **Minimum Usable SubseT**.
- **Should have:** Requirements that should be met are also critical to the success of the project but are not required for delivery within the current timeframe. Target requirements are just as important as mandatory requirements, although target requirements are often not as time-critical or there is another way to fulfil the requirement so that it can be postponed to a later phase. Therefore, it could be said that target requirements are functions that are not critical for implementation but are considered important and of high value to the user.
- **Could have:** Requirements marked as could are desirable but not necessary and could improve usability or customer satisfaction with low development costs. They are usually considered if time and resources allow.
- **Won't have (this time):** Requirements marked as Won't have been agreed as the least critical, least recoverable or not appropriate elements at this time. As a result, Won't requirements are not scheduled into the Delivery Time Box development plan. Won't requirements are either dropped or reconsidered for later phases or projects. However, this does not make them less important. Alternatively, also described as "Would like to have in the future".

All requirements are important, but they are prioritised to achieve the greatest and most immediate (business) benefit early on. Developers will first try to meet all the must have, should have and could have requirements, but should and could have requirements will be the first to be dropped if the delivery schedule seems at risk.

We have adapted this template for the CRISTAL project. The approach is to have all aspects relating to a requirement as compactly as possible at a glance:

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p>Requirement's identifier:</p> <p>REQ- [FU/NFU]- [IT/FR/PO]- (NUMBER)</p>	
Requirement's name	Name of the requirement		
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional/ Non-functional / constraint		Must / Should / Could / Won't Have	
Product (service or functionality)	Use-case		Scenario
Product applying	Which one (if any) or GENERIC		Which one (if any) or GENERIC
Rationale: Why must this requirement be considered for the project.			
Requirement description: A well-formulated description of this requirement.			
Acceptance criteria: Must be met to fulfil the requirement.			
Supporting materials: Links, references, etc			
Requires ethics observance: Mark and write if considered			
Source	Identified by:		Registration date:
EU project, ports observation, stakeholder experience...	PXX [Partner acronym]		dd-MM-yyyy

Figure 18: Requirement Template for Digital Twin Use Cases within CRISTAL

10. CRISTAL Sensor Technologies

The sensor data supplied to the DT is collected via four different sensor technologies. These are briefly presented in the following chapter. The summary is based on the detailed description of the technologies in (D2.1 Interface specification and system architecture preliminary requirements 2023).

10.1. Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS)

'Fibre Bragg Grating' sensors, commonly named 'FBGs', are optical fibre strain sensors. A Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensor is embedded into an optical fibre, a thin glass 'wire'. Inside the fibre, the FBG is built into a short segment about 5 millimetres, which allows to measure the deformations of the fibre structure itself. Cabling can be done with fibre optic cables commonly used for telecommunication applications. In the case of extensive FBG sensor networks, which are required so that the electronic measuring system can be very far away from the sensors, spare cables of already existing telecommunication networks can be used.

Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS) have proved to be an excellent technique for real-time in-situ Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) of civil structures and infrastructures due to numerous advantages, such as small size, light weight, durability, and high bandwidth, which allows a great number of sensors to operate in the same system, and the possibility for the sensors to be integrated within the constructive material, if needed.

In the CRISTAL project, an innovative use of FOS technology is proposed, i.e., to monitor the accumulation of sand/debris along critical sections of waterways to examine the water depth. Towards that the FOS monitoring system is made of a set (possibly, of multiple sets) of submersed scales and one water level gauge (upper level of the water, no water depth). The set of submersed scales shall stay within an area such that the level of the water is the same, as measured by the water level gauge. The set of submersed scales and the water level gauge are all connected to the same FOS Interrogator (data logger) by fiber optic cables. The water level gauge is a solid tube to be installed at the bank. The submersed scales and the fiber optic cables are armored and dredge safe. The FOS Interrogator acquires and processes the raw data of the FOSs, providing the height of the sand in correspondence of each submersed sensor pad. In short, the working principle of the FOS monitoring system implemented for navigability monitoring purposes can be resumed as follow:

- The total pressure on the scale is due to the accumulated sand and the water level.
- The water level is measured by the water level gauge.
- The pressure of the sand is obtained by subtraction, and
- The variation of the height of the sand is therefore calculated.

For both use cases, i.e., navigability and SHM, the FOS technology works with a fully passive optical working principle with no feed of electrical power, which requires less maintenance and fits the three conditions of the field of application.

The FOS system will be prepared as a prototype demonstration in a testbed and characterized simulating realistic condition of clean/turbid water and various sands/stones. Possibly a pilot installation will be tested to test transferability of the results obtained from a prototypical environment to the "real" river section.

Further information about the deployment of the FOS within CRISTAL can be found within D2.1. The matching of the pilots needs without the usage of this sensor will be detailed described within WP7 (D7.5).

10.2. Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)

A radar system transmits radio waves towards a spatial area where targets are located (i.e., "expected features of interest"), from which the waveforms are partially backscattered and received by the radar system a short time later. The intensity and delay time of the returning signal can be used to determine the distance, spatial profile, and composition of the target. Ground penetrating radar systems will be used in CRISTAL. Commercial ground penetrating radar (GPR) systems typically use a multiplexed array of transmitting and receiving antennas housed in a self-contained, moveable enclosure and routed over the surface of the subsurface area for a given scan. The technology used in CRISTAL is called Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) technology.

The equipment is used during maintenance of the lock. The side walls of the lock chamber can be inspected either over the entire surface or with a focus on selected critical areas. The main purpose is to detect potential underground (subsurface) defects and/or critical problems that may become critical at a later stage and would require preventive measures. In doing so, the technology should be usable once for narrow-gauge locks and once for wide-gauge locks. These differ in the type of defects that are to be detected. During maintenance, it is also possible to observe the bottom of the lock chamber, which should be well drained. The performance of the bottom inspection is identical for narrow-gauge and wide-gauge locks.

The subsurface inspection would provide essential information about the structure of the side walls, which is not available for historic locks built over 70-80 years ago. Data processing would allow proper mapping of the existing structures, which is extremely helpful for future maintenance of the older locks.

The equipment could also be used at any time regardless of maintenance. The implementation of this use case is less demanding as it is based on existing practice. The process is the same for narrow-gauge and wide-gauge locks. The main purpose is to identify potential critical problems in the earthwork (e.g., voids, water accumulation, etc.) that may affect the structure of the side walls and become critical at a later stage. However, the use of SIR in specific sectors of a dam is dependent on the water level.

10.3. Acoustic Emission (AE)

Acoustic emission (AE) is elastic radiation generated by the rapid release of energy from sources within a material. These elastic waves are detected by small piezoelectric sensors and converted into voltage signals. Interpretation of the AE signals based on parameters such as duration, peak amplitude and energy, event count, ring-down count and arrival time allows waveform analysis on possible defects, type of defect and location. The overall design of the micro-SHM AE system is a compact, rugged design in a steel housing, with all communication via normal Wi-Fi.

In addition, further peak performance AE devices will be integrated with single AE nodes for easier distribution of AE monitoring in large infrastructures and across the port. As can be seen, in addition to large infrastructures, critical pipes and connections, including critical steel cables and wind generators, can also be monitored.

The technique is well established with thousands of papers to prove that and used in monitoring cases of big infrastructure monitoring cases either for SHM or NDT. In CRISTAL's case it will be used to monitor the good operation of water lock gates (doors). The door consists of two leaves opening horizontal aided by a hydraulic piston. The gates also use in many cases paddles to fill or empty water from the water lock. AE will be used to measure the acoustic imprinting both in time but also in frequency of door operation both in open but also in close operation and the operation of the paddles – if any - and the hydraulic piston, Figure 19. A double system will be used - one deploying sensors across a door leaf and the other capturing data from the piston operation with sensors deployed at the piston. AE as a monitoring system is used during the normal operation of the water lock gate operation, and it does not require any additional requirements.

Figure 19 AE on an industrial hydraulic aluminium extrusion piston

10.4. Intelligent Buoy System (IBS)

The intelligent buoy system for measuring water levels in controlled waterways enables the measurement of the river depth at selected points as well as the measurement of the water level in relation to the underside of the bridge. For this purpose, sonar is combined with a radar sensor that enables the measurement of the distance between the bridge and the water surface. The intelligent buoy system will also measure important river parameters such as water temperature, water velocity and flow direction. The solution will also be equipped with a meteorological measuring station and thus provide information on air temperature, air pressure, wind speed and wind direction. The intelligent buoy system will also count passing ships using multidirectional radar. Other important features of the system are peripheral devices for measuring the clearance under the bridge and a module for ship communication.

11. Use Case analysis

Within this section the use cases within the pilots are described and visualized. Based on them the requirements for the DT are collected. Those are written within the following chapter Requirements. The analysis is based on the results of meetings, workshops, work in collaborative platforms (Miro-Board, Concept-Board, TEAMS), exchanges by mail and exchanges via shared files.

During the requirement evaluation the functionalities of the DT and the SCMS were listed so every partner could adjust. The related data sources and the output consumer were described as well. Additionally, the priority of all functionalities was noted for a common approach of the further development. A list from the status of 03/2023 with all functionalities can be found in the Annex I.

Additionally, the use cases were elaborated in working meetings between the respective pilots and WP5. Thereby, the use case and requirements of the pilots were continuously evaluated, updated, and supplemented if required.

Within the next sections the use cases identified within the pilots are detailed described. In the descriptions of the use cases, individual topics are taken up or mentioned selectively. In particular, the visualisation component of the DT, the DT Smart Monitor, is referred to in various places. This is the GUI component that enables display and interaction.

The use cases are all written with the assumption of availability of suitable data needed for the development of accurate and effective ML algorithms and / or predictions. As these are core services of the DT, this availability of data is one of the highest risks in the development of the DT. In case of data lack, the quality of predictions could suffer. The handling of this risk as well as the concrete data management is described in D5.2. Furthermore, the concrete quality of the available data during the development phase is examined and the actual quality of the predictions and ML algorithms that can be achieved is classified in D5.3.

11.1. Italian Pilot

In this section the DT use cases, UC, are described for the Italian pilot, UC-I. Within the elaboration meetings between WP2, WP7 and WP5 several use cases were defined, namely:

- Navigability of free-flowing waterways (UC-I from 1 to 4)
- Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) of Lock Walls (UC-I 5)
- Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) and Operation Functionality Monitoring (OFM) of Lock Doors (UC-I from 6 to 12)

For each UC-I a prioritisation category has been expressed according the MoSCoW scale previously described; the use cases that are not feasible are prioritized as “Won’t have”, as they will also not be considered within the DT development as part of CRISTAL project.

Use-Case I-1: Fiber Optic Sensor (FOS) Technology for navigability: Visualization of output from FOS sensor measures (Won't have)

This use case relates to the visualization of the continuous and dynamic outputs produced by Fiber Optic Sensors. FOS outputs are in terms of sand height deposited on fixed monitored points within selected sections of the river critical for the navigability; Section 10.1 of this deliverable provides details on how FOS sensors work and how sand height is estimated. In the different monitored points of each monitored critical section the following dataset will be provided. The frequency of the measurement can be set from real-time to a longer period.

The DT can provide a visualization of these FOS outputs, in terms of a 2D or 3D model cross section for each monitored critical section representing both the sand height deposited in the riverbed as well as the water level (available from AIPo as described in Use Case 2).

Further to the graphical representation of FOS results as 2D or 3D models, FOS sensors once installed can feed UC-I-2 as an alternative to the approach currently used for monitoring the sand height in critical sections of the river (i.e., by daily boat bathymetric measurements).

Use-Case I-2: Prediction of water depth (through ML) using hydrological information (Must)

Along the Po River a set of critical points were individuated and observed during last 30 years by AIPo. Based on available data set of daily water depth at each critical point and discharge at monitoring point FRA, AIPo and ENEA will develop and calibrate a ML algorithm capable to estimate the probability (or range) of water depth related to the discharge condition. The ML algorithm will be implemented with actual and forecasted discharges at each monitoring point to predict the changing of the water depth depending on the forecasted flow conditions. The ML algorithm should include the variation related to the riverbed modification recorded in the historical data, especially after a flood event, and at different times of the year, such as winter and in summer. The goal is to predict the expected water depth along several critical points for the next days and check if that could be an issue for the navigability.

Therefore, the 30-year-long historical dataset available at AIPo on actual navigable water depth will be used to train the ML algorithm along with weather forecast (weather information can be collected from open weather forecasts) and water flowing forecasted discharge information.

Data will be accumulated to capture the relation between flow, sand dune movement, and behavior. The goal is to predict how the sand could move the expected water depth along several critical points for the next days, e.g., flood or drought heavy rain is expected and to check if that could be an issue for the navigability. To make a Proof of Concept it will be necessary to check the real sand height in the river. After that it will be possible to compare the result of the calculation with the real measured result. It might then be necessary to adjust the calculation (algorithm or machine learning) after that.

The water level from hydrometer network available at AIPo and the ML outcoming results could be both provided to the DT Smart Monitor, AIPo Dashboard and SCMS, as described in UC-I-3 and UC-I-4. The extent to which it makes sense and is necessary to pass on the water level data already available at AIPo must be determined in detail later.

Use-Case I-3: Display of measured water level from hydrometer network: DT Smart Monitor (Must)

This UC I-3 relates to the display of the hydrological data, i.e., measured water level available from the hydrometer network available at AIPo. These data could be displayed into the DT Smart Monitor, the SCMS and the AIPo Dashboard as well.

Use-Case I-4: Alert functionality for navigability due to hydrological issues (Must)

The DT will calculate the forecasted navigation probability for each reach of the river providing different warning levels like a traffic light (not navigable, doubtful, navigable) for the next days.

This information will be shown in a graphical output and suitable as a technical report (but there won't be a PDF or similar). Before a serious problem occurs, an alert could be given to warn, maintain or to recommend stopping ships in the worst case.

The alert could be provided to the DT Smart Monitor, the SCMS and the AIPo Dashboard as well.

Within figure 20 the use cases UC-I- 1 - 4 related to the navigability of free-flowing waterways are described as a use case diagram.

Figure 20 Use Case Diagram Free-flowing Waterway Navigability (Pilot Italy)

Use-Case I-5: Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) Technology (Won't have)

The SIR Technology generates raw data which will be processed to usable data containing information about the dimensions and functional state index of lock walls. The data contains information about the height, width, depth (thickness) and punctual state of the lock walls. The data also contains information about what material is used and what is inside and behind the walls or if there is a problem. This data will be transferred to the DT.

First, the results (processed data) of the SIR Technology, which is used to analyze lock walls or embankments, must be visualized. The data contains information about the lock walls dimension and functional state. The data will be used to create three-dimensional models of the lock walls. It can be used, e.g., by the infrastructure manager to check the status of the lock and to make further planning of further inspections and/or maintenance. The angle of the view will be changeable.

This is a one-time measurement that is only done once per decade. Which further measures and information can be derived from this measurement will depend on the experience within the project and development process.

The data will be obtained by EUMO and the visualization comes from University Newcastle. AIPO and AIPO Infrastrutture Venete, IV, can provide for the constructive information of the lock; this information will be stored in the DT and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data can be provided to the DT Smart Monitor, AIPO Dashboard and Corridor Management System (SCMS). The DT will be usable for different locks.

Use-Case I-6: Acoustic Emission (AE) System – Display of outputs (Must)

The AE system as a monitoring system generates raw data per hit occurrence with an adjustable threshold, which will be reduced into features like energy, duration, counts, partial frequency power, average frequency, instantaneous frequency and phase, initiation frequency and various other technical features/indicators, demonstrating the functional state of lock doors/gates. This data will be transferred to the DT.

The interval of the measurement can be set when above a certain threshold to reduce the amount of the data. The produced features will be those that will be transferred and not the actual waveform data to reduce the amount of the required data but at the same time keeping the orthogonal constituents of the AE measurements. The analysis and algorithm must be implemented in the DT together with CERTH (AE Team) and provide the result (e.g., a possible gate failure chance providing a heuristic degree of failure confidence), to the DT. The results can be an indicator for future maintenance in dependency of time. The results will be visualized in the DT Smart Monitor presenting a certain lock.

The features/data exported from the AE system and will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The result could be provided to the DT Smart Monitor, DT Alert System, AIPO Dashboard and Corridor Management System (SCMS).

The DT will be usable for different locks.

Use-Case I-7: Alert System - Lock Door (Should)

The results of the analysis of the generated AE system data will be used to implement an alert system for lock doors. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific lock door with a custom threshold for a parameter (e.g., possible gate failure chance). The system now monitors this parameter and as soon the threshold is exceeded, a notification is sent to the subscriber.

It can be used, e.g., by the infrastructure manager to check the status of the lock and to make further planning of further inspections and/or maintenance.

The subscribers and thresholds will be stored. The results will be provided to the subscribers (e.g., SCMS, AIPo Dashboard) and the DT Smart Monitor.

Use-Case I-8: Lock Chamber Dimensions (Should)

The lock chamber dimension changes due to compression by large amounts of water. This means that the lock walls are in “constant motion”, depending on whether the lock is being filled or emptied. The actual space inside the lock chamber is constantly changing. Therefore, the specification of a real usable lock dimension (width, length, height) is required. The lock chamber should be visualized by a 2D/3D model.

The data will be acquired by a user input to the DT Smart Monitor or using the related endpoint and will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor.

Use-Case I-9: General Lock Status (Could)

An entire lock can have several different states (e.g., opened, out of order, under maintenance). These states are visualized and can be changed.

The data will be acquired by a user input to the Smart Monitor or using the related endpoint and will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor, DT Alert System, AIPo Dashboard and SCMS.

Use-Case I-10: General Lock Status - Alert System (Could)

The general state of a lock will be used to implement an alert system for the entire lock state. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific locks general state with an optional duration that state is kept. The system now monitors this lock and as soon as the general state changes, a notification is sent to the subscriber immediately or after the optional time period has expired. In future, local authorities and responsible persons will be informed automatically if the lock is unexpectedly unusable for a specific time period.

The subscribers will be stored. The results will be provided to the subscribers.

Use-Case I-11: Lock General Information Indicators (Could)

There are several parameters that can characterize a lock. Future possible indicators can be the passage time, cost of passage, water consumption, energy consumption, CO2 emission, environmental impact, functional status, and others, that are not known yet. These parameters must be able to be displayed and managed in the DT Smart Monitor as key/value pairs.

The data will be acquired by a user input to the DT Smart Monitor or using the related endpoint and will be stored and can be accessed in the DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor.

Use-Case I-12: Lock Documents (Could)

There are various documents about locks. These documents are stored for a lock with additional information. Furthermore, information can be changed for documents that have already been added. For example, such documents could be construction and circuit plans of certain lock components, or maintenance plans and inspection results.

The data will be acquired by a user input on a kind of DT document overview or using the related endpoint. The data will be stored and can be accessed due to a kind of DT document overview or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to a kind of DT document overview in the DT Smart Monitor.

Within the figure 21 the use cases UC-I- 6 - 12 related to the SHM of the locks are described as a use case diagram.

Figure 21 Use Case Diagram Structural Health Monitoring of a Lock (Pilot Italy)

11.2. French Pilot

In this section the French pilot use cases for the DTs are described.

1. Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) Technology: Visualization of lock walls
2. Acoustic Emission (AE) System: Visualization and forecast of the functional state of lock doors
3. Alert System - Lock Door: Alert on lock door failure chance exceeding pre-set limit
4. Lock Chamber Dimension: Visualization of lock chamber dimensions
5. General Lock Status: Visualization and modification of a general lock status
6. Alert System - General Lock Status: Alert on detection of a general lock status change
7. General Information Indicators: Visualization and modification of general information indicators of locks
8. Documents: Upload and input, visualization and modification of lock related documents and additional information
9. Buoys: Visualization of buoys and related information
10. Alert System - Buoys: Alert on detection of a change in buoy position, that exceeds a pre-set limit

Use-Case F-1: Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) Technology (Must)

The SIR Technology generates raw data (EUMO) which will be processed by UNEW to usable data containing information about the dimensions and functional state index of lock walls. The visualization contains information about the height, width, depth (thickness) and functional state of the lock walls. The data also contain information about what material is used and what is inside and behind the walls. It will also show if there is an abnormality, a difference from the standard wall visuals. This data will be transferred to the DT.

First, the results (processed data) of the SIR Technology, which is used to analyze the lock walls, must be visualized. The data contain information about the lock walls dimension and functional state. The data will be used to create three-dimensional models of the lock walls. It can be used, e.g., by the infrastructure manager to check the status of the lock with assistance from UNEW and to make further planning of further inspections and/or maintenance. The angle of the view will be changeable.

This is a one-time measurement that is only done once per decade. Which further measures and information can be derived from this measurement will depend on the experience within the project and the development process.

The data comes from University Newcastle. The data will be obtained by EUMO, the visualization comes from University Newcastle and VNF will provide the lock information. Information will be stored in the DT and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data can be provided to the DT Smart Monitor and Corridor Management System (SCMS).

The DT will be usable for different locks.

Use-Case F-2: Acoustic Emission (AE) System (Must)

The AE system as a monitoring system generates raw data per hit occurrence with an adjustable threshold, which will be reduced into features like energy, duration, counts, partial frequency power, average frequency, instantaneous frequency and phase, initiation frequency and various other technical features/indicators, demonstrating the functional state of lock doors/gates. This data will be transferred to the DT.

The interval of the measurement can be set when above a certain threshold to reduce the amount of the data. The produced features will be those that will be transferred and not the actual waveform data to reduce the amount of the required data but at the same time keeping the orthogonal constituents of the AE measurements. The analysis and algorithm must be implemented in the DT together with CERTH (AE Team) and provide the result (e.g., a possible gate failure chance providing a heuristic degree of failure confidence), to the DT. The results can be an indicator for future maintenance in dependency of time. The results will be visualized in the DT Smart Monitor presenting a certain lock.

The data comes from the AE system and will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The result will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor, DT Alert System, AIPo Dashboard and Corridor Management System (SCMS).

The DT will be usable for different locks.

Use-Case F-3: Alert System - Lock Door Mechanisms (Must)

The results of the analysis of the generated AE system data will be used to implement an alert system for lock doors. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific lock door with a custom threshold for a parameter (e.g., possible gate failure chance). The system now monitors this parameter and as soon the threshold is exceeded, a notification is sent to the subscriber.

It can be used, e.g., by the infrastructure manager to check the status of the lock and to make further planning of further inspections and/or maintenance.

The subscribers and thresholds will be stored. The results will be provided to the subscribers (e.g., SCMS, AIPo Dashboard) and the DT Smart Monitor.

Use-Case F-4: Lock Chamber Dimensions (Should)

The lock chamber dimension changes due to compression by large amounts of water. This means that the lock walls are in “constant motion”, depending on whether the lock is being filled or emptied. The actual space inside the lock chamber is constantly changing. Therefore, the specification of a real usable lock dimension (width, length, height) is required. The lock chamber should be visualized by a 2D/3D model.

The data will be acquired by a user input to the DT Smart Monitor or using the related endpoint and will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor.

Use-Case F-5: General Lock Status (Could)

An entire lock can have several different states (e.g., opened, out of order, under maintenance). These states are visualized and can be changed.

The data will be acquired by a user input to the Smart Monitor or using the related endpoint and will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor, DT Alert System, AIPO Dashboard and SCMS.

Use-Case F-6: Alert System - General Lock Status (Could)

The general state of a lock will be used to implement an alert system for the entire lock state. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific locks general state with an optional duration that state is kept. The system now monitors this lock and as soon as the general state changes, a notification is sent to the subscriber immediately or after the optional time period has expired. In future, local authorities and responsible persons will be informed automatically if the lock is unexpectedly unusable for a specific time period.

The subscribers will be stored. The results will be provided to the subscribers.

Use-Case F-7: General Information Indicators (Could)

There are several parameters that can characterize a lock. Future possible indicators can be the passage time, cost of passage, water consumption, energy consumption, CO2 emission, environmental impact, functional status and others, that are not known yet. These parameters must be able to be displayed and managed in the DT Smart Monitor as key/value pairs.

The data will be acquired by a user input to the DT Smart Monitor or using the related endpoint and will be stored and can be accessed in the DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor.

Use-Case F-8: Documents (Could)

There are various documents about locks. These documents are stored for a lock with additional information. Furthermore, information can be changed for documents that have already been added. For example, such documents could be construction and circuit plans of certain lock components, or maintenance plans and inspection results.

The data will be acquired by a user input on a kind of DT document overview or using the related endpoint. The data will be stored and can be accessed due to a kind of DT document overview or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to a kind of DT document overview in the DT Smart Monitor.

Use-Case F-9: Buoys (Could)

In our environment there are several buoys whose position and light status is monitored. This data will be provided by the VNF IOT data hub and will be transferred to the DT.

This data is used to create a visualization of buoys and their placement in river basins based on geodata. That will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor or the related endpoint. The data will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor and DT Alert System.

Use-Case F-10: Alert System – Buoys (Could)

The buoys position will be used to implement an alert system. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific buoy position with a custom threshold. The system now monitors the buoys position and as soon buoy's position changes beyond the pre-set threshold, a notification is sent to the subscriber.

In future, the subscriber could send a maintenance team to inspect the related buoy. The subscribers and thresholds will be stored. The results will be provided to the subscribers.

Within figure 22 the use cases UC-F- 1 - 10 are described as a use case diagram.

Figure 22 Use Case Diagram French Pilot

11.3. Polish Pilot

In this section the Polish pilot use cases for the DTs are described.

1. Visualization of an intelligent buoy
2. Visualization of a river
3. Prediction of river conditions
4. Alert System: Navigability alert on current water level
5. Alert System: Navigability alert on predicted river conditions
6. Alert System: Navigability alert on current ice cover
7. Alert System: Navigability alert on barge count

Use-Case Poland P-1: Visualization of an intelligent buoy (Must)

There are several intelligent buoys in our environment. Those buoys provide various data, including water level, ice cover height, temperature, wind speed and barge count. A single buoy is fixed to a location by anchor and ground tackle. Therefore, the position of a buoy can be identified based on coordinates.

The required data is received by accessing an endpoint provided by a data source that uses GS1's EPCIS standard. This data will be transferred to the DT.

Within the DT Smart Monitor, a buoy can be displayed with its collected data including its coordinates. The data will be stored as well.

Use-Case Poland P-2: Visualization of a river (Must)

This use case includes the task of creating a visualization of an area of a river. For this purpose, data collected by intelligent buoys and publicly available data is used. A map can be used to visualize a river with its estuaries and other surroundings. On this map, there are now single data points that represent a single intelligent buoy, for example. These individual data points could now be viewed individually or at all. Furthermore, there is other publicly available data, that could be visualized too (e.g. <http://danepubliczne.imgw.pl/api/data/hydro/> <https://danepubliczne.imgw.pl/api/data/synop/> from public data access info web page <https://danepubliczne.imgw.pl/apiinfo>).

In future, users will be able to draw conclusions about the navigability of the river based on this visualization.

The required data is received by accessing an endpoint provided by a data source that uses GS1's EPCIS standard. The data will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor. The data will be provided to the DT Smart Monitor.

Use-Case Poland P-3: Prediction of river conditions (Could)

The task is to generate predictions of the water level of a river at a specific location by a fixed point in time. This should happen based on the water level of upstream estuaries and locations in the river, that are upstream the point under consideration. Data collected by intelligent buoys and made available by a GS1 standard named EPCIS will be used as base for these predictions. Additional data from existing sources

could be used as well, as far as the quality, format and availability meets the conditions required for their use.

The required data is received by accessing an endpoint provided by a data source that uses GS1's EPCIS standard. These predictions are intended to provide logistic operators and infrastructure managers with tendencies about the evolution of water levels in the river under investigation. This data will be stored and can be accessed via DT Smart Monitor and the related endpoint.

Use-Case Poland P-4: Alert System: Navigability alert on current water level (Must)

As in the use-cases of DT Alert Systems before, the current water level will be used to implement an alert system. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific river location with a custom threshold. The system now monitors the water level and as soon as the current water level changes beyond the pre-set threshold, a notification is sent to the subscriber.

This is to inform actors involved (e.g., logistic operator and infrastructure manager) about current high and low tides, so that predictive measures can be taken if necessary. It might still be necessary to subscribe to the DT Alarm System permanently, or for a certain period, for example for passing barges. These points cannot be determined yet but could be observed in the later stages of the project process.

The subscribers will be stored. The notifications will be provided to the subscribers.

Use-Case Poland P-5: Alert System: Navigability alert on predicted river conditions (Must)

The predicted water level will be used to implement an alert system. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific river location with a custom threshold. The system now monitors the water level and as soon as the predicted water level changes beyond the pre-set threshold, a notification is sent to the subscriber.

This is to inform involved actors (e.g., logistic operator and infrastructure manager) about upcoming and unexpected high and low tides, so that predictive measures can be taken if necessary. It might still be necessary to subscribe to the DT Alarm System permanently, or for a certain period, for example for passing barges. These points cannot be determined yet but could be observed in the later stages of the project process.

The subscribers will be stored. The notifications will be provided to the subscribers.

Use-Case Poland P-6: Alert System: Navigability alert on current ice cover (Must)

As in the use-cases of DT Alert Systems before, the ice cover thickness will be used to implement an alert system. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific river location with a custom threshold. The system now monitors the ice cover thickness and as soon as the ice cover thickness changes beyond the pre-set threshold, a notification is sent to the subscriber.

Currently, ice corridors are monitored, if at all, by manual sightings and subsequent settings of markers along the river to notify respective actors. By automatically measuring the ice cover and implementing it in the DT Alert System, automatic notifications can be sent to the subscribers. Whether this goal is technically

achievable and whether it is possible to draw conclusions about the presence or thickness of the ice cover is not known yet and will be observed during the project process.

The subscribers will be stored. The notifications will be provided to the subscribers.

Use-Case Poland P-7: Alert System: Navigability alert on barge count (Must)

The intelligent buoys are able to track the number of passing barges. This barge count is now used to implement a DT Alert System. Therefore, the number of passing barges could be used to conclude the traffic situation on the point under consideration at a specific location on a river (barge position).

In reality, users could now subscribe to this barge count of buoys with certain thresholds. This would enable the system to notify users as soon as a critical traffic situation occurs on the river under consideration. This could, for example, be caused by blocked traffic or reduced amount of traffic due to environmental influences.

In the future, this barge count could also provide information about the estimated time of arrival of individual barges in order to predict delays. The subscribers will be stored. The notifications will be sent to the subscribers.

Within the figure 23 the use cases UC-P- 1 - 7 are described as a use case diagram.

Figure 23 Use Case Pilot Poland

11.4. Digital Twin Mock-Up

After the collection of use cases and the formulation of those as text, mockups of a possible GUI of the DT were created. These self-designed graphics are intended to depict a possible DT's Smart Monitor. Accordingly, they are only sample images of a software application that does not yet exist.

With those the functionalities of the DT and the several user perspectives could be discussed with visual support. The look of the DT's Smart Monitor can deviate.

Mock-Up Use Case Lock (Predictive Maintenance)

This section shows Mock-Ups of the DT Smart Monitor related to a physical lock described within the French pilot. The lock use cases within the Italian pilot are oriented to the French pilot, except for the SIR. Therefore, those Mock-Ups could be used as well to discuss a DT Smart Monitor for those use cases. These Mock-Ups consider the SIR to get a holistic view of it.

Figure 24 shows an overview of one lock and the collected data. Some sensor information is displayed as well, a detailed description of the SIR output can be found within figure 26 and the following description.

Figure 24 DT Smart Monitor Mock-Up - Overview (Lock)

Figure 25 (a) presents SIR raw data in the form of rotational A-scan transects of subsurface topography. Raw rotational transect data is a series of successive A-scan signal intensity profiles, taking the form of lightweight Touchstone files listing step-swept scanning frequencies of the emitted measurement signal and returning complex frequency measurements of the partially backscatter reflection signals. Individual datapoints within each A-scan encode the intensity of the returning backscattered waveform (i.e., 'strength' of reflection event) and two-way signal propagation time (i.e., 'depth' of reflection event).

The antenna head is moved across the lock wall in a 2D-gridded pattern, with movement down columns taking priority. Data post processing by UNEW will return volumetric 3D renders of subsurface geometry as illustrated in (b). Encoded features will be automatically characterized by bespoke processing algorithms. The DT will only have access to the final characterized volumetric dataset.

Figure 25 (a) Collection of SIR raw data and (b) Characterised 3D Feature Output post processing

Starting from this page, overview pages as about the related documents can be displayed (see Figure 26).

Figure 26 DT Smart Monitor Mock up - Overview Files (Lock)

The gained alerts and related information can be displayed as well. Within this overview all information about the alert, the time of occurrence and possibly additional information given by the user itself can be seen (see Figure 27).

Figure 27 DT Smart Monitor Mock up - Overview Alerts (Lock)

Mock-Up Use Case Water-Level

The second part of Mock-Ups is about visualization of the Smart Buoys described within the Polish pilot. Those will be shown on a map to get an overview of all installed buoys and their submitted data. They can be individually selected to see their detailed information displayed (see Figure 28).

Figure 28 Digital Twin Mock-Up - Overview (Buoys)

Additionally, for each buoy some collected data will be displayed, as for example the water level of the last weeks and the predicted water level for the coming days (see Figure 29).

Figure 29 Digital Twin Mock-Up - Detail View (Buoys)

11.5. Sequence diagrams

Based on the described use cases within the pilots, several interactions between users or systems and the DT were identified. Within this section those were described via sequence diagrams. This allows relationships between users and the DT to be identified, as well as making some deductions for the later creation of the architecture.

To get access to the DT users must be authenticated as seen in Figure 30. Therefore, as described previously Keycloak will be used to handle the Authentication and to match security requirements.

Figure 30 Sequence Diagram - User Authentication

A holistic overview of the physical entities will be given through several data inputs as sensor data, external data as well as the opportunity to upload individual documents related to the monitored infrastructure. Uploaded documents can also be displayed to use them during operation planning or maintenance (see Figure 31 and 32).

Figure 31 Sequence Diagram - Data Upload

Figure 32 Sequence Diagram - Document Overview (Displaying Documents)

As the information contained within the documents could change over time, the option to make notes related to those should be given as shown in Figure 33. These notes could also include information about past maintenance operations or comparable.

Figure 33 Sequence Diagram - Document Add Note

Besides sensors which are collecting and sending data continuously, some sensor data as for example from the SIR will be collected once and then uploaded to the DT. Additionally, to the data collected by the CRISTAL sensors and the pilot partners, some data from external sources will be collected. Those data need to be requested actively from the DT itself (see Figure 34).

Figure 34 Sequence Diagram – Single Data Input & External Data Acquisition

The data from the SIR and the AE system will also contain information about the lock related to specific locations of the lock. Therefore, a visualization in 3D should be considered as shown in Figure 35 and 36.

Figure 35 Sequence Diagram - Visualization Lock Walls (3D)

Figure 36 Sequence Diagram - Visualization Lock Doors (3D)

After collecting data from sensors, they will be used to generate predictions related to the river and infrastructure conditions which could have impact on operations decisions. The notification of the users is handled via an alert system (see Figure 38). Thus needs a subscription of the users interested in the alerts (see Figure 37).

Figure 37 Sequence Diagram - User Subscription Alert System

Figure 38 Sequence Diagram - Notification Alert System

As users are not only interested in alerts as well as in predictions of the general infrastructure conditions, but subscribers can also be notified in case of predictions as shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39 Sequence Diagram - Notify on Predictions

Beside notifications of actual alerts and predictions, the request of predictions is provided for the SCMS (see Figure 40).

Figure 40 Sequence Diagram - SCMS Retrieve Predictions

The predictions will be generated by a component of the DT itself (see Figure 41). The point of time when predictions will be generated will be defined within the deployment. This way a suitable time schedule can be defined and re-validated with the pilot partners and related to the chosen machine learning method.

These decisions will be written down and explained within D5.3.

Figure 41 Sequence Diagram - ML/AI Module Generate Predictions

12. Relation between DT and Synchro-Modal Corridor Management System

Based on the conditions and requirements of the project pilots which were captured in the previous chapters, a concept and an architecture for the CRISTAL DT can be created in the next sections of this document. However, an essential aspect in this first step is not only to identify and collect the available data and the pilots' needs but also to consider the needs of data consumers. Based on the data and needs mapping, several requirements have become clear which the DT must address by generating new knowledge and predictions. This knowledge and predictions form a context to the collected data, which can provide other systems with decision bases for current and future logistics planning.

The CRISTAL SCMS is such a system and is accordingly to be considered as a consumer of the DT's output. This section therefore discusses what information the DT can provide to the SCMS and what requirements emerge in this process.

One important output of the DT relates to the prediction of disruptions and their impacts on waterway navigability. For the SCMS, time specifications are primarily important, i.e., when the event (disruption) can occur with what probability and in particular for how long. The DT data produced, which allow conclusions to be made regarding navigability, include:

- Water level (alerts and predictions)
- Ice cover thickness (alerts and predictions)
- Infrastructure failure predictions (within CRISTAL focused on locks)

As stated above, this data needs to be contextualized. Therefore, the impact of the events related to the data and predictions need to be evaluated as well. The data related to the river itself can be used to gain insights into which ships can currently navigate on the river. For this purpose, free waterways and water depth can be compared with dimensions of ship types. Data about the parts of the infrastructure will be able to provide input especially when they are expected to fail. Based on historical data and technical specifications, it could be possible to extract what time expenditure can be expected for their maintenance.

To be able to make this contextualization, additional data must be used in addition to predictions. This data includes indicatively the following information:

- Ship categories and their specifications
- Historical data about maintenance operations
- Technical guidelines about maintenance operations and processes
- Weather data and predictions

During the analysis of the pilot needs and their data, it became clear that no usable historical data on maintenance would (or might) be available. To address this problem, static tables with estimated time requirements for different categories of maintenance operations and fixed practices/processes will be created based on expert views to be used by the DT. For example, this information will be able to correlate with the results of the AE system and thus assign a duration for repairing a possible malfunction in a lock

door and restore its normal operation. This information will be stored and can form the data basis for prediction models in the future.

In addition, an attempt will be made to categorise malfunctions and thus help decide for example, whether a malfunction is a minor problem that can be resolved within a few hours and therefore no action is required regarding logistics operations (e.g., rerouting, mode change) or is a major problem that will result in a lock being closed for several days. This classification will be carried out together with CERTH using the results of the AE system as an example.

On the other hand, the analysis of the connection between the DT and the SCMS has shown that it would be redundant for the DT to store data about ship categories. As the SCMS will store this data for additional services that will be provided, this could lead to problems in case that the categories between the two systems are not identical. To avoid the overlapping work and issues of data interpretation, the DT will not store such list of ship categories. Instead, the DT will calculate vessel specifications that meet the river status of navigability (e.g., maximum barge draft allowed) and the SCMS will compare those with its own ship categories.

To ensure that the collected data from the pilots and the produced predictions will meet the needs of the SCMS, these specifications will be considered within the requirements in the following section of the document.

13. Requirements

This chapter contains the business cases that emerges from the key performance indicators (KPIs) for business cases as given in D1.1 Stakeholder Requirements and Business Scenarios, chapter 4.2. Further, this chapter extends these requirements by obvious requirements for DT that should address the implementation of the individual Use Cases of the pilots.

The requirements are divided into General Requirements and requirements related to the specific pilots. Additionally, the requirements are allocated to the use cases identified within the previous chapter. The templates filled in with all necessary and detailed information about the requirements can be found within the Annex II. The tables shown in this chapter include the unique IDs, use cases and names of requirements. The category describes the difference between functional and non-functional (see also section 9.4). To support the development of the DT all requirements are prioritized as described before in descending order of priority: Must (M), Should (S), Could (C) and Won't have (W).

13.1. General Requirements

The general requirements refer to functionalities the DT needs in general to ensure a proper use. Therefore, these are valid for all pilot DTs. An example of this is the guarantee of safety aspects explained here. Securing all accessible interfaces should be implemented as a standard and basically concerns all points for data exchange and thus of course all DTs. At this point, various categories are addressed that apply superordinate.

Table 5 General Requirements

ID	Use Case	Name	Category	Priority
NFU-GE-1	Data Storage	Encrypted data storage	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-2	Security	Encrypted communication	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-3	Security	Endpoint security	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-4	Security	Credentials Access	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-5	Security	Standard password strength	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-6	Security	Automatic Logout	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-7	Legal	Compliance	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-8	Legal	Data privacy	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-9	Legal	Third party dependencies	Non-Functional	S

NFU-GE-10	Integrity	Data integrity detection	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-11	Reliability	Restart	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-12	Recovery	Recovery	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-13	Usability	User-friendly UI	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-14	Usability	Multilingual support	Non-Functional	C
NFU-GE-15	Usability	Barrier-free accessibility	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-16	Usability	European language support	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-17	Documentation	Source code comment	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-18	Documentation	Software documentation	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-19	Documentation	API documentation	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-20	Source code quality	Source code quality	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-21	Source code versioning	Git history	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-22	Performance	System robustness	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-23	Operational	Expected environment	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-24	Operational	Standard International Connection	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-25	Operational	Different Time Zones	Non-Functional	S
NFU-GE-26	Maintainability & Support	System deployment	Non-Functional	M
NFU-GE-27	Testability / Maintainability	Testability of the application	Non-Functional	S

13.2. Requirements of the Italian Pilot

This section lists the requirements related to the Italian pilot use cases. As previously described some requirements were prioritized as “Won’t have” during the adjustments of the pilot deployment regarding the FOS use case implementation. At this point, the requirements refer to the Italian pilot, but some requirements, for example for the use case lock, can also be found in the French use case.

Table 6 Requirements Italian Pilot

ID	Use Case	Name	Category	Priority
FU-IT-1	River – Water-Depth (AIPO Dashboard)	Acquire data on water depths from AIPO dashboard	Functional	M
FU-IT-2	River – Dune Height (FOS)	Acquire data in dune heights (FOS)	Functional	W
FU-IT-3	River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)	Calculate drivable water depth (FOS)	Functional	W
FU-IT-4	River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for real-time monitoring of drivable water depth (FOS)	Functional	W
FU-IT-5	River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)	Navigability alert for users on drivable water depth (FOS)	Functional	W
FU-IT-6	River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)	Generate drivable water depth forecast (FOS)	Functional	W
FU-IT-7	River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)	Navigability alert for users on forecast of drivable water depth (FOS)	Functional	W
FU-IT-8	River – Dune Height (FOS)	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for historical data on dune heights (data by FOS)	Functional	W
FU-IT-9	River - Water Depth	Acquire data on water depth	Functional	M
FU-IT-10	River - Water Depth	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for historical data on water depth (data by AIPO hydrometer network)	Functional	M
FU-IT-11	River - Water Depth	Generate predictions of the water depth	Functional	M

FU-IT-12	River - Water Depth	Navigability alert for users on water depth data	Functional	M
FU-IT-13	River - Water Depth	Predict warning levels on navigability	Functional	M
FU-IT-14	River - Water Depth	Warning levels for users on water depth data	Functional	M
FU-IT-15	River - Water Depth	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for visual representation of warning levels	Functional	M
FU-IT-16	River – Ship characteristics	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for a ship problem overview	Functional	C
FU-IT-17	River – Hydrological issues	Navigability alert for users due to hydrological issues	Functional	C
FU-IT-18	Lock Door – AE System	Acquire data on gate failure chance	Functional	M
FU-IT-19	Lock Door – AE System	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for historical data on gate failure chance (data by AE System)	Functional	M
FU-IT-20	Lock Door – AE System	Generate predictions of the gate failure chance	Functional	M
FU-IT-21	Lock Door – AE System	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for visual representation of the lock	Functional	M
FU-IT-22	Lock Door – AE System	Maintenance alert for users on gate failure predictions	Functional	S
FU-IT-23	Lock Door – AE System	Maintenance alert for users on AE system data	Functional	S
FU-IT-24	Data Accessing on pilot	Endpoints for accessing pilots’ data	Functional	S
FU-IT-25	Lock Chamber Dimensions	Acquire data of lock chamber dimensions	Functional	C
FU-IT-26	Lock Chamber Dimensions	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock chamber dimensions	Functional	C
FU-IT-27	General Lock status	Acquire data about the general lock status	Functional	C

FU-IT-28	General Lock status	Navigability alert for users on general lock status	Functional	C
FU-IT-29	General Information Indicators	Acquire data about general lock related information indicators	Functional	C
FU-IT-30	General Information Indicators	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display general lock related information indicators	Functional	C
FU-IT-31	Documents	Acquire dock related documents	Functional	C
FU-IT-32	Documents	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock related documents	Functional	C
NFU-IT-1	Documents	Lock related document privacy	Non-Functional	C
NFU-IT-2	Lock Door – AE System	Gate failure chance accuracy	Non-Functional	C

13.3. Requirements of the French Pilot

This section lists the requirements related to the French pilot use cases.

Table 7 Requirements French Pilot

ID	Use Case	Name	Category	Priority
FU-FR-1	Lock Wall - SIR	Acquire data of a lock walls punctual state and dimensions	Functional	M
FU-FR-2	Lock Door – AE System	Acquire data on gate failure check	Functional	M
FU-FR-3	Lock Door – AE System	Generate predictions of the gate failure chance	Functional	M
FU-FR-4	Lock Wall – SIR Lock Door – AE System	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for visual representation of the lock	Functional	M
FU-FR-5	Lock Door – AE System	Maintenance alert for users on gate failure prediction	Functional	M
FU-FR-6	Lock Door – AE System	Maintenance alert for users on AE system data	Functional	M

FU-FR-7	Lock Chamber Dimensions	Acquire data of lock chamber dimensions	Functional	S
FU-FR-8	Lock Chamber Dimensions	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock chamber dimensions	Functional	S
FU-FR-9	General Lock Status	Acquire data about the general lock status	Functional	C
FU-FR-10	General Lock Status	Navigability alert for users on general lock status	Functional	C
FU-FR-11	General Information Indicators	Acquire data about general lock related information indicators	Functional	C
FU-FR-12	General Information Indicators	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display general lock related information indicators	Functional	C
FU-FR-13	Documents	Acquire dock related documents	Functional	C
FU-FR-14	Documents	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock related documents	Functional	C
FU-FR-15	Buoys	Acquire buoy data	Functional	M
FU-FR-16	Buoys	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display buoys data	Functional	M
FU-FR-17	Buoys	Maintenance alert for users on buoys position data	Functional	M
FU-FR-18	Data Accessing on pilot	Endpoints for accessing pilots' data	Functional	M
FU-FR-19	Real-time data out of EURIS	Vision of the current and future state of the network for users	Functional	W
FU-FR-20	Camera based analysis of infrastructure	Automatic detection of disorders on complete river	Functional	W
FU-FR-21	Virtual lock	Training testbed for maintenance teams on a virtual lock	Functional	W
FU-FR-22	Infrastructure Management Decision Assistant	Decision advice assistant for current and future infrastructure components while consider the overall environment	Functional	W

FU-FR-23	Maintenance Team Decision Advice Assistant	Decision advice assistant for maintenance teams	Functional	W
NFU-FR-1	Documents	Lock related document privacy	Non- Functional	C
NFU-FR-2	Lock Door – AE System	Gate failure chance accuracy	Non- Functional	C

13.4. Requirements of the Polish Pilot

This section lists the requirements related to the Polish pilot use cases.

Table 8 Requirements Polish Pilot

ID	Use Case	Name	Category	Priority
FU-PO-1	Intelligent Buoys	Acquire data on buoys from GS1 EPCIS	Functional	M
FU-PO-2	Intelligent Buoys	Visualization of a buoys data in DT Smart Monitor	Functional	M
FU-PO-3	Intelligent Buoys	Visualization of a river in DT Smart Monitor	Functional	M
FU-PO-4	Intelligent Buoys Water Level	Prediction of river conditions	Functional	C
FU-PO-5	Intelligent Buoys Water Level	Navigability alert on predicted river conditions	Functional	M
FU-PO-6	Intelligent Buoys Water Level	Navigability alert on current water level	Functional	M
FU-PO-7	Intelligent Buoys Ice Cover	Navigability alert on current ice cover	Functional	M
FU-PO-8	Intelligent Buoys Barge Count	Navigability alert on barge count	Functional	M
FU-PO-9	Data Accessing on pilot	Endpoints for accessing pilots' data	Functional	M

NFU-PO-1	Intelligent Buoys Water Level	Predicted river condition accuracy	Non- Functional	C
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13.5. Requirements of the Synchro-Modal Corridor Management System

This section lists the requirements related to the SCMS. An overview about additional requirements were given within chapter 12.

Table 9 Requirements SCMS

ID	Use Case	Name	Category	Priority
FU-CM-1	River – Water Depth	Calculate drivable water depth (ship specifications)	Functional	S
FU-CM-2	River – Water Depth	Predict drivable water depth (ship specifications)	Functional	S
FU-CM-3	River – Water Depth	Navigability alert on drivable water depth (ship specifications)	Functional	S
FU-CM-4	Intelligent Buoys Ice Cover	Predict ice cover	Functional	C
FU-CM-5	Intelligent Buoys Ice Cover	Navigability alert on predicted ice cover	Functional	C
FU-CM-6	Lock Door	Determine maintenance duration based on static table (AE system)	Functional	S
FU-CM-7	Lock Door	Maintenance alert on lock door downtime	Functional	S

14. Digital Twin Architectural Design

The following architecture is based on the findings of the state-of-the-art analysis and the concrete requirements listed in chapter 13. The analysis of the requirements has shown that the creation of a generally valid architecture for the DT is possible, but the realisation will then have to take place in several different DTs. There is no use case and no application that is currently used across all three pilots but could be. For example, in the Polish pilot project, no lock currently needs to be mapped, but in Italy and France it does. This also means that, in principle, the implementation of a DT for locks is planned, as well as the mapping of buoys and the pre-calculation of water levels in river areas. This is therefore not an explicit 1-to-1 relationship between pilots and DT, but rather a thematic assignment. In addition, one twin per lock will be created to do justice to the specifics. However, the design of the DT is intended to be generally valid and can therefore be used for different types of locks.

As mentioned in the first chapter as an outcome from the research work, there is no single solution for a DT architecture. Nevertheless, in basic research and, for example, in the SPHERE project presented in chapter 3.3, the starting point is a layered architecture. This offers many design options and makes it possible to flexibly cover a wide range of requirements. For the requirements and subsequent realisation in CRISTAL, this is also a very suitable solution here.

Based on the reference layer architectures an architecture for the CRISTAL DT was developed. This architecture shown in figure 42 is divided into different layers, which are separated from each other depending on their concern. There is a Data Visualization Layer, a Data Processing Layer, a Semantic Layer, and a Security Layer within the components of the DT. The Data Acquisition Layer is outside the DT and is provided externally and will therefore not be discussed further. Further information about the data acquisition within CRISTAL is provided by the deliverables submitted from WP2 and WP5.

The individual components within the layers are deployed in docker containers. This serves the purpose of loose coupling between the individual components and leads to scalability. The scalability is required because not only a single application is deployed for all pilots or DTs. Depending on the pilots and their use cases, different implementations of the individual components are deployed in corresponding containers.

At this point in the project, no final decision has been made about the distribution of the data from a technical point of view. The architecture approach for the DT has therefore been designed to be as open as possible. This means that, in principle, data can be received and sent (push vs. pull). Whether this is done later via a central component of the overall architecture (keyword middleware), which is implemented only for the sensor data, for example, or directly in 1-to-1 relationships is irrelevant for the time being. It is then a matter of determining the exchange format and the data structure. This opens the possibility of processing real-time data as well as one-off information regardless of the data size. This implementation also meets the established requirements.

The next sections describe the several layers and their components in more detail.

Figure 42 Digital Twin Software Architecture

14.1. Data Processing Layer

The basic components of the DT are located within the data processing layer. A Java Spring Boot backend is the central module for data processing and data distribution. All operations necessary for the pilots and their use cases are performed here.

The adapters represent the entry point for external data. The implementations of the adapters are adapted to sensor devices and external systems and their specific protocols. The adapters handle the data mapping and data pre-processing so that the backend can use the external data at all. By implementing additional adapters, the approach of expandability of the system can be achieved. If we take a closer look at the function of the adapters for the individual pilots, it becomes clear that here, for example, the data from the SIR and AE analysis of the lock use cases is fed into the system. This functionality can also be applied to other incoming data from other sensors or platforms.

Other tasks of the Java Spring Boot backend are the further data processing and the storage of data in respective databases and the access to these data. Data persistence services are provided to store historical data from external sensor devices and systems as needed. In turn, the data history services provide access to this data. Needed historical data from sensor devices and external systems are stored inside a NoSQL database called CouchDB. Such databases are particularly suitable for persisting certain sensor data such as point clouds, which are difficult to map to a specific data model. For example, exactly this type of data must be processed by the DT. For the pilot, this means that the handling of the historical sensor data from AE or SIR analysis from the lock use cases is managed here. The data is persisted into a NoSQL database and can also be made available again for further processing. This method of operating can also be adapted for the other use cases of the pilots. The openness and flexibility of the architecture naturally allows the CouchDB mentioned here as an example to be replaced without any problems.

The services belonging to the category of Data Processing Service are responsible for the further processing of data according to the implemented use cases. They handle the processing of general backend data and static data of external devices and systems and their handling with a SQL database based on database management system PostgreSQL. Furthermore, those services must perform required logical operations and, if necessary, trigger accesses to the functionalities of the ML/AI-Module in order to retrieve predictions. Regarding the pilots, for example, the required steps to generate predictions about a gate failure chance retrieved from the AE sensor data of the lock use are performed here. The required accesses to the implementations in the ML/AI-Module adapted to this use case are also performed at this level. Other operation related to the category of Data Processing Service could also be the creation of 3D models of the locks for the DT Smart Monitor. So, in general this category of services describes the logical operations that are necessary to fulfil the requirements of our use cases.

The implementation of the DT Alert System requires two types of components. The data subscription services manage the subscribers who have applied for notifications of specific values with different parameters. Furthermore, the alert system services are used to monitor the respective values and to send notifications to the respective subscribers if necessary. Using the AE sensors, for example, which are considered here again, this means that external systems can subscribe to a certain lock door and to the respective gate failure chance while specifying thresholds. If these actual thresholds are reached, or a periodically generated prediction predicts the reaching of one of these thresholds, the system registers this by monitoring the related values and comparing it with the data of the subscribers. In this case, an alarm would be sent back to the external system or individual users. Similar implementations would occur for similar use cases of other pilots.

In addition, there must be several types of components to manage access to the DT itself and to provide the required interfaces. This is done by the controllers that receive and process the requests to the interfaces of the DT. These controllers are accessed via the REST standard. The implemented REST APIs are required both by external systems, which want to receive specific data, and by components that are located within the DT, such as the DT Smart Monitor in the Data Visualization Layer and the respective ML/AI-Module. For data that is automatically provided by the DT, there are various data brokers. These work according the publish subscribe pattern. The responding data is then automatically sent to a specific topic, which in turn can be subscribed to receive the provided data. Therefore, external systems can receive data from the DT without a specific request. For the DT Smart Monitor in the Data Visualization Layer, a kind of data broker is also implemented, which supplies the required real-time sensor and external system data e.g., via WebSocket. It is also designed as a loose coupling here to separate the concerns and make it possible to change the frontend.

For the ML/AI-Module, at this stage of the project, no more detailed statement can be made about the exact architecture. The structure of this module will be determined in a later stage of the project.

14.2. Data Visualization

The Data Visualization Layer contains the DT Smart Monitor. This is a web application developed for each pilot and their use cases. It displays a view of the respective twin and contains a view of all related information. The DT Smart Monitor is a stand-alone component, that accesses the required data from the Data Processing Layer via interfaces. For this purpose, the DT Smart Monitor requests actively data via the REST API or also receive real-time sensor and external system data via the use of WebSocket.

A NGINX web server runs in the respective docker container of the DT Smart Monitor, which contains the content and transfers it to the requesting web browsers. For the development itself Angular is used. Angular is a free and open-source framework to create web applications.

14.3. Semantic Layer

The data model of the DT is outsourced to the Semantic Layer. This has several advantages. On one side, the different implementations of the DT can implement the data model themselves, while it can be centrally managed and provided. On the other side, the data model can be deployed in several versions, while different versions of the DT are being developed. This leads to more flexibility in the development process and makes it easier to expand the components in the future. In fact, the data model is added with the respective version as a dependency to the Java Spring Boot backend located in the Data Processing Layer.

Another component of the Semantic Layer is an API documentation which complies to the specification of OpenAPI. Through the dependency to SwaggerUI this documentation will be provided in a human readable format. This also makes it relatively easy to get an overview of existing interfaces from the outside and, if necessary, to use them provided that it makes sense and is possible from a security point of view.

14.4. Security Layer

The Security Layer contains a Keycloak authentication server. This is a component to validate the access to the DT. Keycloak requires a database to separate the individual realms and manage their groups, roles, users, and clients.

Validation of access is always necessary when an attempt is made to access the components of the DT from outside. Therefore, validation is necessary when accessing the DT Smart Monitor and when accessing the provided endpoints of the Java Spring Boot backend.

Components such as databases and the ML/AI-Module should not be reachable from outside and so do not require validation by an authentication server. Nevertheless, the databases are secured via the standard security mechanisms of the individual database management systems.

In addition, the section 14.5 provides an example of a possible implementation within the framework of CRISTAL. Requirements such as the possibility of separating different infrastructures, the differentiation according to work areas and task areas in a country as well as the simple division according to countries

were also taken into account. This means, for example, that the lock in the Italian pilot is separated from the lock in France in terms of rights and duties. Overall, the system is very flexible and offers many different combination possibilities and thus variable control of access and restrictions to the DTs. This also applies to other systems and not only to users.

14.5. User access rights

It is suitable to use a framework that manages access rights to consider requirements regarding security. An example implementation could be realized using the access management of Keycloak. Each pilot has separate access rights. This means that each pilot can only manage his own DTs. For this purpose, three realms are created, one realm for a pilot. A realm helps administer users, credentials, roles, and groups. Information about the Keycloak access rights and handling in this and the next sections was taken from the source Server Administration Guide (Server Administration Guide 2023).

Thereby, it is important that each DT is considered separately among the pilots. Each pilot gets its own user groups with specific permissions for functionalities. Groups help e.g., to separate and organize locks within a pilot. This means that users can be assigned to a group, which in turn have access to special locks.

To distinguish between user rights, it is necessary to have roles. First, an admin role will be created and is allowed to access everything inside of the DT. Furthermore, a manager role will be created. The manager is allowed to read, write, and execute inside the DT. The last role will be the employee. The employee can only read inside of the DT.

To secure the applications in the DT, clients must be created in Keycloak. Clients are applications and services which can request Keycloak to authenticate a user. In addition, clients can also query identity information or an access token to securely invoke other services which are secured by Keycloak. In case of the DT there will be three clients. These three clients will be, on the one hand, the API to give systems information about DT. Next come the external systems that need an access token to call the API. The last client will be the frontend also called DT Smart Monitor.

Figure 43 Access Rights Digital Twin

Figure 43 shows the different systems and users and their rights to the DT components. First there are the users which can be for example the Content Management System/AIPo dashboard users, infrastructure managers, maintainer, and local authorities. These users will be able to access the DT Smart Monitor and the Alert System and have the authority to access, update and download information from the DT Smart Monitor. Also, they can access the Alert System and configure alerts and get notifications when an alert occurs.

External systems are allowed to get alert information but cannot access raw sensor data. Moreover, the external systems can request the API for information about the DTs. For example, if the SCMS wants to retrieve information about the SIR, it must authenticate to the Keycloak to get an access token. In the next step, the API can be accessed using this token to retrieve that information. The access token is validated by Keycloak and without it the authentication is not possible.

The admin is allowed to access all components except for the API. For example, the admin can view the alarms created and can manage the configuration files and the composition of the DTs.

Access to the application must be actively granted, for example by means of a user account and the associated rights and roles. This ensures that external users do not have access to the applications. In this way, each pilot can only manage their own DTs, so that they cannot access others by accident.

15. Class Design

This chapter focuses on the presentation of the classes needed to implement the digital twin. Here the first drafts of the class design for the lock use case for the French and Italian pilots, the buoy use case for the Polish and French pilots, and the water level and navigation use case for the Italian pilot are presented.

15.1. Lock Use Case

Figure 44 Class Diagram - Use Case Lock

The first draft for the class diagram of the lock use case can be seen in Figure 44. There are several class objects that are necessary to represent a lock. The lock data is time-stamped to indicate when the data was last modified. A lock contains general information about its status, a fixed address, a contact, which could be a person or an organization, additional transit information and several documents. Furthermore, a lock has a certain dimension, which differs from the real usable space of the lock chamber due to, for example, external water pressure. All this is represented here. In addition to general information about the lock, information about the lock doors derived from the AE system and the lock walls examined by SIR technology will also be available here. The required predictions and the functional state of those individual components are saved here as well.

15.2. Buoy Use Case

Figure 45 Class Diagram - Use Case Buoy

In the class diagram in Figure 45, the first draft of the class design for the buoy use case is presented. This diagram covers both, the buoy use case for the Polish and French pilots. For each buoy, an object of the buoy class is created for the river in which it is located. In the polish pilots’ case, these rivers can also be estuaries that flow into the river under consideration for the pilot, as the water level in the main river depends on those estuaries. For the French pilot the buoy positions are mainly relevant. A buoy can collect various data about itself and its environment. Furthermore, this information will be used to make predictions about future water level, possible ice thickness and the traffic situation base on the barge count. Therefore, different Prediction-Classes can be found here in the diagram.

15.3. Water Level Use Case

Figure 46 Class Diagram - Use Case Water Level

This diagram represents a draft of the class design of the water level und drivable water depth use cases of the Italian pilot (see Figure 46). Here a river is observed, which has different river parts. For each of these river parts an indication of the current water level and the drivable water depth can be given. Furthermore, this information and other historical data not presented here will be used to create predictions about the water level and the drivable water depth. It is also important to save these predictions with time spans and therefore the attributes “predictionFrom” and “predictionTill” can be found in the classes as well as “predictedAt” to represent a certain point of time.

16. Conclusions

This deliverable contains the outcome of *T5.1 Requirements Engineering, Architecture & System Design*. Within this task first state-of-the-art research of digital twins regarding existing infrastructure and IoT platforms as environment of the CRISTAL DT was done. Based on this research a definition of the DT could be written down as well as several decisions for the analysis and design process could be made. Those definition and methodology decisions were described as well. Second, this methodology was used to evaluate the use cases and engineer the requirements of the CRISTAL pilots and the SCMS. After the basic work has been done, the document then focuses more on the substantive issues. Detailed descriptions of the use cases and the resulting requirements are listed and detailed in the appendix of the deliverable. First mock-ups for a visualisation idea of the requirements and sequence diagrams of the use cases are included. Those are the basis for the CRISTAL DT architecture as one main result of this document. Lastly, the first-class diagrams were developed as a building block of the following software development work.

We have gained and elaborated three main insights. One main conclusion could be drawn within the state-of-the-art research, as we found out, no general suitable definition or reference architecture of digital twins are existing. Those depend on concrete use cases or objectives. Therefore, we oriented to the pilot use cases and focused on the common requirement analysis. The CRISTAL DT architecture was developed from scratch, suitable for the CRISTAL pilots and with inclusion of the research outcomes. The second main conclusion was found during the use case analysis, as there is no use case valid for all pilots. Even use cases valid for two use cases are not identical, but only widely overlapping. The CRISTAL DT architecture was created from components and several instances will be developed for each pilot use case. Thus, the architecture is suitable for all pilots and the overlaps can be used as synergies. The last main conclusion is about the quality of available data. During the use case analysis, it becomes clear that not several, but the most functionalities of the DT are based on predictions and/or machine learning techniques. To develop these functionalities the quality of used data is very crucial for the usability and precision. Since this risk could not be sufficiently remediated at this time and is part of the Data Management of T5.2, it is carried forward as a potential risk into the other tasks. It has also been communicated to the consortium so that all are aware of it and can act accordingly.

In this process some best practices could be identified. One was to define the methodology and to structure the process of requirements engineering and use case analysis before starting. Thus, all partners were aware of the different steps of the process and all outcomes are comparable as well. The evaluation respectively existing standards simplifies the reading for third parties. Additionally, the research about already existing projects focused on digital twins enabled us to understand the state-of-the-art architectures and definitions very quickly. Also, as no general architectures are available, the existing projects and their architectures were used to compare ours and detect potential vulnerabilities. Nevertheless, one lessons learned raised as well. An interim version of this document was provided for all partners to avoid long feedback loops. Since many of the results had already been largely elaborated and some partners wanted to check input regarding their own technologies, to work with everyone in one document at the same time seemed to be good. This allowed many comments and additions to be made in a short time. However, the simultaneous editing also required a high degree of moderation. Next time, we would provide an interim version again, but with clear rules for editing to reduce the overload.

Following this document *D5.2 Data integration and data model* will be submitted as described within the GA, in which the data management for the whole project integrating the DT will be described.

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19. Appendices

Annex I

WP	TASK	Functionality (if determined)	Functionality description	Required data	Data source	Produced data	Data receiver / consumer	
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display water level	Display water level (AIPo) in DT Smart Monitor	Water level	AIPo water level	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display historical data	Display historical data on water level (AIPo) in DT Smart Monitor	Historical data on water level	AIPo historical data set	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Generate predictions on water level using a machine learning module or algorithm	Generate predictions on water level using a machine learning module or algorithm. The goal is to predict the expected water depth along several critical points for the next days and check if that could be an issue for the navigability.	Water level Historical data on water level Weather data	WP2 AIPo water level AIPo historical data set Weather data (external)	prediction data	WP5.3 Alert system WP 5 (Self) AIPo dashboard	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display predicted water level	Take the predicted water level and display them in the Smart Monitor (DT).	Prediction of water level	WP5 (Self)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Navigability Alert for Users on reaching limit of calculated water level	Take the predicted water level and push an alert, when the value exceeds or falls below a pre-set navigability limit.	Prediction of water level A user set limit and /or limit from AIPo system	WP5 (Self) + User input and/or AIPo dashbaord (Threshold /Limit)	Alert	SCMS AIPo dashboard	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Generate a prediction of drivable depth (predicted water level)	Use ML modules to generate a prediction of water level using historically data of water depth and weather data for a specific time period.	Needed is the historical data of water level and weather data at the same area/coordinates including timestamp.	WP2 AIPo water level Weather data (external)	long term prediction data	WP5.3 Alert system WP 5 (Self) AIPo dashboard	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display prediction of water level	Take predicted water level and display them in Smart Monitor (DT).	Prediction of water level	WP5 (Self)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Navigability Alert for Users on reaching limit of predicted water level	Take the predicted water level and push an alert, when the value exceeds or falls below a pre-set navigability limit.	Prediction of water level A user set limit and /or limit from AIPo system	WP5 (Self) / (WP2?) User input and/or AIPo dashboard (Threshold /Limit)	Alert	SCMS AIPo dashboard	Must

WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Predict warning levels on navigability	The system must predict warning levels for navigability on water depth for the next days. Warning levels consist of: not navigable, doubtful, navigable	Water level Historical data on water level Weather data	WP2 AIPO water level AIPO historical data set Weather data (external)	prediction data	SCMS AIPO dashboard WP 5 (Self)	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Warning levels for users on water depth data	The system must be able to predict warning levels on water depth data when reaching defined thresholds.	Water level Historical data on water level Weather data	WP2 AIPO water level AIPO historical data set Weather data (external)	prediction data	SCMS AIPO dashboard WP 5 (Self)	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display warning level	Display the rivers navigability status, including a river section warning level.	Prediction of warning levels	WP5 (Self)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Navigability Alert for Users on warning levels	Before a serious problem due to hydrological issues, an alert could be given to warn, maintain or to recommend stopping ships in the worst case. The system must be able to alert users on a ships navigability status reaching defined thresholds, e.g. a certain warning level.	Prediction of warning levels A user set limit and /or limit from AIPO system	WP5 (Self) User input and/or AIPO dashboard (Threshold /Limit)	Alert	SCMS AIPO dashboard	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display the 2D/3D model of a lock.	Display the 2D/3D model of a lock by using data based on AE System in Smart Monitor (DT)	Data array of the lock doors. Width, Height, Depth (Thickness), State	AE System (WP 5.2)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display the infrastructure status of a lock door.	Recieve data of the acoustic monitoring of a lock door. Display the infrastructure status of a lock door in Smart Monitor (DT).	Data of the acoustic monitoring of a lock door including area and timestamp.	AE System (WP 5.2)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Generate a prediction of the gate failure chance of a lock door.	Use ML modules to generate a prediction of the chance a gate failure of a lock door can appear using the information of the acoustic emission system.	Needed is the current functional state index of the door and historical data of the lock door.	AE System (WP 5.2)	long term prediction data for failure scenarios	GUI of DT Alert System SCMS AIPO dashboard	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display the gate failure chance of a lock door.	Display the predicted gate failure chance of a lock door using the generated prediction. Results are	prediction of gate failure chance of a lock door	WP5 (Self)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must

			displayed in the Smart Monitor (DT).					
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Maintenance Alert for Users on reaching limit of predicted gate failure chance of a lock door	Take the predicted gate failure chance of a lock door and push an alert, when the value exceeds or falls below a pre-set maintenance limit.	prediction of gate failure chance of a lock door A user set limit	WP5 (Self) User input (threshold /limit)	Alert	SCMS AIPO dashboard	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Maintenance Alert for Users on reaching a defined limit using current state of the lock door.	Take current AE system data and push an alert, when a value exceeds or falls below a pre-set maintenance limit.	Current functional state index of the lock door. A user set limit	WP8 User input (threshold /limit)	Alert	SCMS AIPO dashboard	Must
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display real dimension of the lock chamber.	Display real dimension (width, length, height) of the lock chamber. Maybe create a 3D visualization. The dimension of the lock chamber changes due compression by large amounts of water.	Real data (due compression of the wall by large amounts of water): Width, Height, Depth (Thickness)	WP5	Visual data	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Functionality to insert real dimension data of the lock chamber.	Add functionality to add real dimension (width, length, height) of the lock chamber. The dimension of the lock chamber changes due compression by large amounts of water.	Real data (due compression of the wall by large amounts of water): Width, Height, Depth (Thickness)	GUI Input and/or API Input (WP5)	Visual data or textual data	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display the general status of the lock.	Display the general status of the lock (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	gener lock status (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	GUI Input and/or API Input (WP5)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Add interface to set the general status of the lock.	Add an interface to set the general status of the lock. (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	general lock status (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	GUI Input and/or API Input (WP5)	data about the general status of the lock (e.g. out of order / under maintenance / opened)	GUI of DT Alert system	Could
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Alert about the general lock status in some szenarios.	Push an alert, when a specific general lock status is set.	general lock status (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	WP5 (Self)	Alert	SCMS Crisis Management (WP3)	Could

WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Display some lock related information indicators,	Display some lock related information indicators. Future possible indicators: passage time cost of passage water consumption energy consumption CO2 emissions environmental impact functional status and others (not known yet)	Lock indicators: There is (nearly) no data available for the lock. In the future it should be added manually to the application.	GUI Input and/or API Input (WP5)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Functionality to upload lock related documents.	Add functionality to upload lock related documents. (e.g.: construction plans, circuit diagrams, maintenance plans, checklists). Also information about the storing location (e.g.: a directory or database) should be added.	Documents	User	Visual data documents	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Functionality to add information about the lock manually and upload documents	Add functionality to append information about the lock and uploaded documents. (e.g. if the uploaded document is a checklist or a planned task, the user would provide further information for the individual steps or mark them with a status (e.g.: pending, in progress, done...)).	Documents	User	Visual data documents + notes	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Calculate drivable water depth (ship measurements)	To contextualize, a maximum ship draught must be calculated.	Water level River related information	Buoy data (WP8) Pilot	Drivable water depth	SCMS	Should
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Predict drivable water depth (ship measurements)	To contextualize, a maximum ship draught must be predicted for a given time.	Water level River related information	Buoy data (WP8) Pilot	prediction of drivable water depth	SCMS	Should
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Navigability alert on drivable water depth (ship measurements)	The system must be able to alert users when the predicted drivable water depth changes.	Prediction of drivable water depth	WP5 (Selft)	Alert	SCMS	Should
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Determine maintenance duration based on static table (AE-System)	To contextualize, a category of infrastructure maintenance or failure must be tied to a downtime duration. The information about the infrastructure event comes from the AE-System and a static table.	Predicted AE Data Static Table of maintenance durations	AE System (WP 5.2) Pilot for the static table	Determine downtime data	SCMS	Should
WP5	5.3 Italian Pilot	Maintenance alert on lock door downtime	The system must be able to alert users when a downtime is foreseeable and how long it will take.	Predicted AE Data Static Table of maintenance durations	AE System (WP 5.2) Pilot for the static table	Alert	SCMS	Should

WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Display the 2D/3D model of a lock.	Display the 2D/3D model of a lock by using data based on a subsurface inspection radar technology in Smart Monitor (DT)	Data array of the lock walls State of the lock Planned data: Width, Height, Depth (Thickness)	SIR Technology (WP2 Task 2.2)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Display real dimension of the lock chamber.	Display real dimension (width, length, height) of the lock chamber and create a 3D visualization. The dimension of the lock chamber changes due compression by large amounts of water.	Real data (due compression of the wall by large amounts of water): Width, Height, Depth (Thickness)	WP5	Visual data	GUI of DT	Should
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Functionality to insert real dimension data of the lock chamber.	Add functionality to add real dimension (width, length, height) of the lock chamber. The dimension of the lock chamber changes due compression by large amounts of water.	Real data (due compression of the wall by large amounts of water): Width, Height, Depth (Thickness)	GUI Input and/or API Input (WP5)	Visual data or textual data	GUI of DT	Should
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Functionality to upload lock related documents.	Add functionality to upload lock related documents. (e.g.: construction plans, circuit diagrams, maintenance plans, checklists). Also information about the storing location (e.g.: a directory or database) should be added.	Documents	User	Visual data documents	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Functionality to add information about the lock manually and upload documents .	Add functionality to append information about the lock and uploaded documents. (e.g. if the uploaded document is a checklist or a planned task, the user would provide further information for the individual steps or mark them with a status (e.g.: pending, in progress, done...)).	Documents	User	Visual data documents + notes	GUI of DT	Could

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WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Display some lock related information indicators,	Display some lock related information indicators. Future possible indicators: passage time cost of passage water consumption energy consumption CO2 emissions environmental impact functional status and others (not known yet)	Lock indicators: There is (nearly) no data available for the lock. In the future it should be added manually to the application.	GUI Input and/or API Input (WP5)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Display the general status of the lock.	Display the general status of the lock (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	general lock status (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	GUI Input and/or API Input (WP5)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Add interface to set the general status of the lock.	Add an interface to set the general status of the lock. (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	general lock status (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	GUI Input and/or API Input (WP5)	data about the general status of the lock (e.g. out of order / under maintenance / opened)	GUI of DT Alert system	Could
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Alert about the general lock status in some scenarios.	Push an alert, when a specific general lock status is set.	general lock status (e.g.: out of order / under maintenance / opened)	WP5 (Self)	Alert	SCMS Crisis Management (WP3)	Could
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Display the infrastructure status of a lock door.	Receive data of the acoustic monitoring of a lock door. Display the infrastructure status of a lock door in Smart Monitor (DT).	Data of the acoustic monitoring of a lock door including area and timestamp.	AE System (WP 5.2)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Generate a prediction of the gate failure chance of a lock door.	Use ML modules to generate a prediction of the chance a gate failure of a lock door can appear using the information of the acoustic emission system.	Needed is the current functional state index of the door and historical data of the lock door.	AE System (WP 5.2)	long term prediction data for failure scenarios	GUI of DT Alert System SCMS	Must
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Display the gate failure chance of a lock door.	Display the predicted gate failure chance of a lock door using the generated prediction. Results are displayed in the Smart Monitor (DT).	prediction of gate failure chance of a lock door	WP5 (Self)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must

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WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Maintenance Alert for Users on reaching limit of predicted gate failure chance of a lock door	Take the predicted gate failure chance of a lock door and push an alert, when the value exceeds or falls below a pre-set maintenance limit.	prediction of gate failure chance of a lock door A user set limit	WP5 (Self) User input (threshold /limit)	Alert	Alert System	Must
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Maintenance Alert for Users on reaching a defined limit using current state of the lock door.	Take current AE system data and push an alert, when a value exceeds or falls below a pre-set maintenance limit.	Current functional state index of the lock door. A user set limit	AE System (WP 5.2) User input (threshold /limit)	Alert	Alert System	Must
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Display buoy data	Create a visualization of buoys and their placement in river basins based on geodata	Buoy data of: buoy position buoy light status	WP8 VNF IOT data hub	Visual data	GUI of DT	Could
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Maintenance alert for users on change of the buoy position over a custom threshold	Push an alert, when the buoy position changes beyond a pre-set threshold.	Buoy data of: buoy position user threshold	WP8 VNF IOT data hub User input	Alert	Alert System	Could
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Determine maintenance duration based on static table (AE-System)	To contextualize, a category of infrastructure maintenance or failure must be tied to a downtime duration. The information about the infrastructure event comes from the AE-System and a static table.	Predicted AE Data Static Table of maintenance durations	AE System (WP 5.2) Pilot for the static table	Determine downtime data	SCMS	Should
WP5	5.3 French Pilot	Maintenance alert on lock door downtime	The system must be able to alert users when a downtime is foreseeable and how long it will take.	Predicted AE Data Static Table of maintenance durations	AE System (WP 5.2) Pilot for the static table	Alert	SCMS	Should
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Visualization of an intelligent buoy	Display current intelligent buoys data in Smart Monitor (DT). The buoys provide various data, including water level, ice cover height (not known yet), temperature, wind speed and barge count. A single buoy is fixed to a location by an anchor and ground tackle. Therefore, the position of a buoy can be identified based on coordinates.	Buoy data (GS1's EPCIS standard) of: water temperature water level wind speed barge count ice cover height (not known yet) position (coordinates)	Buoy data (WP2/WP 9)	Raw data from buoys sent to DT and then used by Smart Monitor for their visualisation	GUI of DT	Must

WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Visualization of a river	<p>Present a visualization of an area of a river with its buoys. For this purpose, data collected by intelligent buoys and, if possible, publicly available data is used. A map can be used to visualize a river with its estuaries and other surroundings. On this map, there are now single data points, that represent a single intelligent buoy, for example. These individual data points could now be viewed individually or at all. Furthermore, there is other publicly available data, that could be visualized too (e.g. http://danepubliczne.imgw.pl/api/data/hydro/ https://danepubliczne.imgw.pl/api/data/synop from public data access info web page https://danepubliczne.imgw.pl/apiinfo).</p>	<p>Bouy data (GS1's EPCIS standard) of: water temperature water level wind speed barge count ice cover height (not known yet) position (coordinates)</p> <p>Publicly available data as suggested in functionality description</p>	Bouy data (WP2/WP 9)	Visual data	GUI of DT	Must
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Prediction of river conditions	<p>The task is to generate predictions of the water level of a river at a specific location by a fixed point in time. This should happen based on the water level of upstream estuaries and locations in the river, that are upstream the point under consideration. Data collected by intelligent buoys and made available by a GS1 standard named EPCIS will be used as base for these predictions. Additional data from existing sources could be used as well, as far as the quality, format and availability meets the conditions required for their use.</p>	<p>Bouy data (GS1's EPCIS standard) of: water temperature water level wind speed barge count ice cover height (not known yet) position (coordinates)</p> <p>Publicly available data at least partly available as mentioned above</p>	Bouy data (WP2/WP 9)	Predictions about future water level and visualised by DT Smart Moitor	WP5 (SELF)	Could
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Navigability Alert on reaching a defined limit of water level	<p>The current water level will be used to implement an alert system. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific river location with a custom threshold. The system now monitors the water level and as soon the current water level changes beyond the pre-set threshold, a notification is sent to the subscriber.</p>	<p>Bouy water level data (GS1's EPCIS standard)</p>	<p>Bouy data (WP2/WP 9)</p> <p>User input (threshold /limit)</p>	Alert sent to the DT Alert System subscribers	SCMS	Must

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WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Navigability alert on predicted river conditions	The predicted water level will be used to implement an alert system. In fact, users can subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific river location with a custom threshold. The system now monitors the water level and as soon the predicted water level changes beyond the pre-set threshold, a notification is sent to the subscriber.	Buoy water level data (GS1's EPCIS standard)	Bouy data (WP2/WP 9) User input (threshold /limit)	Alert sent to the DT Alert System subscribers	SCMS	Must
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Navigability alert on current ice cover height	The ice cover thickness will be used to implement an alert system. Users will be able to subscribe to the DT Alert System for a specific river location with a user defined threshold. The system will allow monitoring of the ice cover thickness and as soon as the ice cover thickness changes beyond the pre-set threshold, a notification will be sent to the subscriber.	Buoy water level data (GS1's EPCIS standard)	Bouy data (WP2/WP 9) User input (threshold /limit)	Alert sent to the DT Alert System subscribers	SCMS	Must
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Navigability alert on barge count	The barge count will be used for the implementation of a DT alert system for the conclusion of the traffic situation at the point of interest at a specific location on a river (barge position). The users will be able to define their individual thresholds for the observed number of barges, so that the system would be able to inform the users as soon as a critical traffic situation occurs on the river in question. This would allow monitoring and, if necessary, reaction when traffic becomes critical.	Buoy barge counter data (GS1's EPCIS standard)	Bouy data (WP2/WP 9) User input (threshold /limit)	Alert sent to the DT Alert System subscribers	SCMS	Must
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Calculate drivable water depth (ship measurements)	To contextualize, a maximum ship draught must be calculated.	Buoy water level data River related information (GS1's EPCIS standard)	Bouy data (WP2/WP 9) Pilot	Drivable water depth	SCMS	Should
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Predict drivable water depth (ship measurements)	To contextualize, a maximum ship draught must be predicted for a given time.	Buoy water level data River related information (GS1's EPCIS standard)	Bouy data (WP2/WP 9) Pilot	Prediction of drivable water depth	SCMS	Should
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Navigability alert on drivable water depth (ship measurements)	The system must be able to alert users when the predicted drivable water depth changes.	Prediction of drivable water depth	WP5 (Self)	Alert	SCMS	Should

WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Predict ice cover	The IoT buoy technology of a polish pilot should be used to generate predictions on ice cover height to improve the infrastructure and navigability. For example, based on existing data, predictions could be made about adjacent river ice cover development.	Buoy data of ice cover height	WP5 (Self)	Prediction of ice cover thickness	SCMS	Could
WP5	5.3 Polish Pilot	Navigability alert on predicted ice cover	The system must be able to alert SCMS when there could be issues due to predicted ice cover.	Buoy data of ice	WP5 (Self)	Alert	SCMS	Could

Annex II

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-1</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Encrypted data storage</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>Data Storage</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The Digital Twin must store its data encrypted.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stored data must be encrypted 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-2</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Encrypted communication</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT components</p>		<p>Security</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The communication between the DT and its components must be encrypted. The communication between the DT and external components must be encrypted.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The communication between DT and its components must be encrypted - The communication between DT and external components must be encrypted 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-3</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Endpoint security</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT endpoints</p>		<p>Security</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The endpoints must be secured by default.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Every endpoint must be secured by default - Only authorized users can use the respective endpoints 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-4</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Credentials Access</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Security</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The DT Smart Monitor is only accessible with correct credentials.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DT Smart Monitor must be secured by a login functionality - Correct credentials must be required to access the DT Smart Monitor 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-5</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Standard password strength</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor & endpoints</p>		<p>Security</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The users password strength must meet a certain standard to be considered as secured.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User passwords must have a minimum length - User passwords must use different types of characters 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-6</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Automatic Logout</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Security</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The DT Smart Monitor must be able to logout users after a certain duration of inactivity</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The DT Smart Monitor must be able to logout users after a certain duration of inactivity 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-7</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Compliance</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT components</p>		<p>Legal</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The DT and its components must respect all local compliances, laws and regulations.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must respect all local laws and regulations 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-8</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Data privacy</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT components</p>		<p>Legal</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must consider about data privacy.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system secures private data - The system is GDPR conform 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-9</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Third Party Dependencies</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT components</p>		<p>Legal</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must consider about using third party dependencies.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system should only use third party licences that are open source compliant - The system should only use third party licences that are secure 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-10</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Data integrity detection</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT endpoints</p>		<p>Integrity</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to detect incorrect data inputs</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to detect incorrect data inputs - The system must be able to stop incorrect data inputs - The system must be able to notify related users about incorrect data inputs 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-11</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Restart</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT components</p>		<p>Reliability</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to restart in the case of unexpected shutdowns.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p>				
<p>- The system must be able to restart in the case of unexpected shutdowns</p>				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-12</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Recovery</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT storage</p>		<p>Recovery</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to create backup data.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p>				
<p>- The system must be able to create backup data.</p>				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-13</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>User friendly UI</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Usability</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The UI should be user friendly and responsive.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The UI must be user friendly - The UI must be responsive - The UI must be easy to use - The UI must be easy to learn 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-14</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Multilingual Support</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Usability</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> There are many people in the project with different main languages who all want to use the DT.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The DT Smart Monitor created must support different languages.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The DT Smart Monitor must support different languages 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-15</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Barrier-free accessibility</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Usability</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The GUI should support barrier-free accessibility.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tooltips and explanation of important input fields. - Font size should be readable - Colours and contrasts should be clearly visible 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-16</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>European language character support</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Usability</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to handle all European language character formats for the pilots.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to handle all European language character formats for the pilots. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-17</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Source code comments		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Non-functional		Should		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Source Code		Documentation	France, Italy, Poland	
<p>Rationale: In the interest of reuse and maintainability of the created source code, the code should be sufficiently commented. This is also important in the context of a possible open-source strategy.</p>				
<p>Requirement description: The created source code must contain sufficient comments so that it can be understood and used by third parties.</p>				
<p>Acceptance criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Classes are commented - Methods are commented - Fields are commented 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-18</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Software documentation		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Non-functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Documentation		Documentation	France, Italy, Poland	
<p>Rationale: In the interest of reuse and maintainability of the created source code, the code should be sufficiently commented. This is also important in the context of a possible open-source strategy.</p>				
<p>Requirement description: A software documentation is to be created for the DT.</p>				
<p>Acceptance criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Software documentation must be created - The ARC42 software documentation template should be used 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-19</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		API documentation		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Non-functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Documentation		Documentation	France, Italy, Poland	
<i>Rationale:</i> In the interest of reuse and maintainability of the created source code, the code should be sufficiently commented. This is also important in the context of a possible open-source strategy.				
<i>Requirement description:</i> An API documentation must be created for the usable endpoints				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An API documentation must be created for the usable endpoints - The API documentation should follow the standard format of OpenAPI 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-20</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Source code quality		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Non-functional		Should		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Source Code		Source Code Quality	France, Italy, Poland	
<i>Rationale:</i> The created source code should be of a certain quality. This is also important in the context of a possible open-source strategy.				
<i>Requirement description:</i> The created source code should have a certain quality.				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Source code should not contain code smells - Source code should not contain bugs. - Source code should not contain vulnerabilities. - Source code should not contain duplicated lines. 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-21</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>	Git history			
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>		<i>Status</i>
Non-functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>		<i>Scenario</i>
DT Source Code		Source Code Versioning		France, Italy, Poland
<i>Rationale:</i> The created source code should be of a certain quality. This is also important in the context of a possible open-source strategy.				
<i>Requirement description:</i> Git must be used to version the created source code.				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Git must be used to version the created source code - Changes must be made in new branches and not in the main branch - Commit messages must be meaningful - Commit messages must contain correct information about the author - Old branches that are no longer relevant must be removed 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-22</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>	System robustness			
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>		<i>Status</i>
Non-functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>		<i>Scenario</i>
DT Smart Monitor		Performance		France, Italy, Poland
<i>Rationale:</i>				
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be failure tolerant. The system should be error resistant in the case of incorrect inputs and unexpected failures.				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be error resistant 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-23</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Expected environment</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Operational</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be operable through a browser.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The DT Smart Monitor must be operable through a browser. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-24</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Standard Internet Connection</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Operational</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be usable using a standard internet connection</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A standard internet connection must be sufficient to use the DT Smart Monitor 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-25</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Different Time Zones</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT components</p>		<p>Operational</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to handle timestamps from different time zones.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to handle timestamps from different time zones 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-26</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>System deployment</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Components</p>		<p>Maintainability & Support</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to use its components in individual containers that are loosely coupled.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The components must be able to build and deploy as single application containers. - The components must be easy to deploy and install. - The components must be easy to maintain. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-GE-27</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Testability of the application</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT components</p>		<p>Testability/Maintainability</p>		<p>France, Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The created source code must be testable and must have a certain test coverage. The created tests must run successful.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The created source code must be testable - The created source code must have a certain test coverage - The tests must run successful 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-FU-IT-1</p>	
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Acquire data on water depths from AIPO Dashboard	
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>
Functional		Must	
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>
DT Data Processing		River - Water Depth (AIPO Dashboard)	Italy
<i>Rationale:</i>			
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive data on water depths from AIPO Dashboard.			
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to receive data on water depths from AIPO Dashboard - The system must be able to store the related data - The system must be able to process related data 			
<i>Supporting materials:</i>			
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>			
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-FU-IT-2</p>	
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Acquire data on dune heights (FOS)	
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>
Functional		Won't Have	
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>
DT Data Processing		River – Dune Height (FOS)	Italy
<i>Rationale:</i>			
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to acquire data on dune heights measured by the Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS)			
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to receive data on dune heights measured by the Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS) - The system must be able to store the related data - The system must be able to process the related data 			
<i>Supporting materials:</i>			
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>			
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>

CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier:		REQ-FU-IT-3
Requirement's name		Calculate drivable water depth (FOS)		
Category	Type	Priority	Status	
Functional		Won't Have		
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case	Scenario	
DT Data Processing		River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)	Italy	
Rationale:				
Requirement description: The system must be able to calculate the drivable water depth using current water depth and dune heights.				
Acceptance criteria:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to calculate drivable water depth using current water depth & dune heights - The system must be able to store the related data The system must be able to process related data				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:		Registration date:

CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier:		REQ-FU-IT-4
Requirement's name		Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for real time monitoring of drivable water depth (FOS)		
Category	Type	Priority	Status	
Functional		Won't Have		
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case	Scenario	
DT Smart Monitor		River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)	Italy	
Rationale:				
Requirement description: The system must provide a GUI using the DT Smart Monitor for the user to monitor the calculated drivable water depths.				
Acceptance criteria:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to display a 2D model of an area of the river - The system must be able to display the drivable water depth for the related area of the river - The system must be able to access required data in order to visualize it 				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:		Registration date:

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-5		
Requirement's name				
Navigability alert for users on drivable water depth (FOS)				
Category		Type	Priority	Status
Functional			Won't Have	
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case		Scenario
DT Alert System		River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)		Italy
Rationale:				
Requirement description: The system must be able to alert users when drivable water depth exceeds or falls below a pre-set navigability limit.				
Acceptance criteria:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when the drivable water depth exceeds a given threshold - Users must be notified when the drivable water depth falls below a given threshold Users must be able to subscribe on the drivable water depth with a given threshold				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:	Registration date:	

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-6		
Requirement's name				
Generate drivable water depth forecast (FOS)				
Category		Type	Priority	Status
Functional			Won't Have	
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case		Scenario
DT Data Processing and DT Predictions		River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)		Italy
Rationale:				
Requirement description: The system must generate a forecast of drivable water depths within a pre-set time period using dune height predictions and water level. The dune height predictions are generated by using the machine learning module.				
Acceptance criteria:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User input of time period must be possible - The system must be able to generate predictions on drivable water depth for a given time period or point in time 				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:	Registration date:	

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-7	
Requirement's name		Navigability alert for users on forecast of drivable water depth (FOS)	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Won't Have	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case		Scenario
DT Alert System	River – Drivable Water Depth (FOS)		Italy
Rationale:			
Requirement description: The system must be able to alert users on calculated water depth forecasts.			
Acceptance criteria:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when a forecasted water depth exceeds beyond a given threshold - Users must be notified when a forecasted water depth falls below a given threshold Users must be able to subscribe on a forecasted water depth with a given threshold			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:		Registration date:

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-8	
Requirement's name		Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for historical data on dune heights (data by FOS)	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Won't Have	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case		Scenario
DT Smart Monitor	River – Dune Height (FOS)		Italy
Rationale:			
Requirement description: The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for looking at historical data on dune heights by using data collected by Fiber Optic Sensors (FOS).			
Acceptance criteria:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to display historical data on dune height The system must be able to access required data in order to visualize it			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:		Registration date:

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-IT-9</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Acquire data on water depth</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>	<p><i>Scenario</i></p>	
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>River – Water Depth</p>	<p>Italy</p>	
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to acquire data on river depth measured by the water depth historical data set (AIPo)</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to retrieve historical data on water depth - The system must be able to store the related data - The system must be able to process the related data 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>	<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-IT-10</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for historical data on water depth (data by AIPo hydrometer network)</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>	<p><i>Scenario</i></p>	
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>River – Water Depth</p>	<p>Italy</p>	
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for looking at historical data on water depth using data collected by AIPo hydrometer network.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to display historical data on water depth - The system must be able to access required data in order to visualize it 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>	<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>	

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-11	
Requirement's name		Generate Predictions of the water depth	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario	
DT Data Processing and DT Predictions	River – Water Depth	Italy	
Rationale: The goal is to predict the expected water depth along several critical points for the next days and check if that could be an issue for the navigability.			
Requirement description: The system must generate predictions of the water depth, e.g. using a machine learning module or algorithm			
Acceptance criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to generate predictions of the water depth within a time period 			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-12	
Requirement's name		Navigability alert for users on water depth data	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario	
DT Alert System	River – Water Depth	Italy	
Rationale: Before a serious problem due to water depth occurs, an alert could be given to warn, maintain or to recommend stopping ships in the worst case.			
Requirement description: The system must be able to alert users on water depth data reaching defined thresholds.			
Acceptance criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when a river sections water depth exceeds beyond a given threshold - User must be able to subscribe on a river sections water depth with a given threshold 			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-13	
Requirement's name			
Predict warning levels on navigability			
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario	
DT Data Processing and DT Predictions	River – Water Depth	Italy	
Rationale:			
Requirement description: The system must predict warning levels for navigability on water depth for the next days. Warning levels consist of: not navigable, doubtful, navigable			
Acceptance criteria:			
- The system must be able to generate warning levels for navigability within a time period			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-14	
Requirement's name			
Warning levels for users on water depth data			
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario	
DT Alert System	River – Water Depth	Italy	
Rationale:			
Requirement description: The system must be able to predict warning levels on water depth data when reaching defined thresholds.			
Acceptance criteria:			
- Users must be notified when a river section warning level changes - User must be able to subscribe on a river section warning level			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-FU-IT-15</p>	
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for visual representation of warning levels</p>	
<p><i>Category</i></p>	<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>	<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>River – Water Depth</p>	<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> The user needs an overview of warning levels and its navigability data.</p>			
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the DT Smart Monitor for the user to monitor the rivers navigability status, including a river section warning level.</p>			
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to display a river section - The system must be able to display a river sections navigability data - The system must display the warning level of the river section - The system must display the warning level of certain ship classes - The system must be able to access required data in order to visualize it 			
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>			
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>			
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>	<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-FU-IT-16</p>	
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for a ship problem overview</p>	
<p><i>Category</i></p>	<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>	<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>River – Ship characteristics</p>	<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> The user needs an overview of which ships have bigger navigability problems than others.</p>			
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the DT Smart Monitor for the user to monitor ship navigability problems, including draught information.</p>			
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to display a river section - The system must be able to display a river sections ship data - The system must display the ship status, e.g., draught, warning level - The system must be able to access required data in order to visualize it 			
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>			
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>			
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>	<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

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<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-FU-IT-17</p>	
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Navigability alert for users due to hydrological issues	
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>
Functional		Could	
<i>Product</i> (Service/Functionality)	<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Alert System	River – Hydrological issues	Italy	
<i>Rationale:</i> Before a serious problem due to hydrological issues occurs, an alert could be given to warn, maintain or to recommend stopping ships in the worst case.			
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users on a ships navigability status reaching defined thresholds, e.g. a certain warning level.			
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when a ships navigability status changes - User must be able to subscribe on a ships navigability status 			
<i>Supporting materials:</i>			
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>			
<i>Source</i>	<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-18	
Requirement's name		Acquire data on gate failure chance	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case		Scenario
DT Data Processing and DT Predictions	Lock Door - AE System		Italy
Rationale: A measurement with an AE system is performed to inspect the doors of a lock. The functional state and dimension are measured. In future, this data could help to plan inspections and maintenance of lock doors.			
Requirement description: The system must be able to take in data gate failure chance from the acoustic emission system.			
Acceptance criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to receive data about the possible failure chance of a lock door - The system must be able to store the related data - The system must be able to process the related data 			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-19	
Requirement's name		Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for historical data on gate failure chance (data by AE System)	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case		Scenario
DT Smart Monitor	Lock Door – AE System		Italy
Rationale:			
Requirement description: The system must provide a GUI using the DT Smart Monitor for looking at historical data on lock doors functional state and gate failure chance collected by an AE System.			
Acceptance criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to display historical data on lock doors functional state - The system must be able to display historical data on gate failure chance - The system must be able to access required data in order to visualize it 			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-20	
Requirement's name		Generate Predictions of the gate failure chance	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario	
DT Data Processing and DT Predictions	Lock Door - AE System	Italy	
Rationale: A measurement with an AE system is performed to inspect the doors of a lock. The functional state and dimension are measured. In future, this data could help to plan inspections and maintenance of lock doors.			
Requirement description: The system must generate predictions of the gate failure chance, e.g. using a machine learning module or algorithm			
Acceptance criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to generate predictions of the gate failure chance within a time period 			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-FU-IT-21</p>	
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for visual representation of the lock	
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>
Functional		Must	
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>
DT Smart Monitor		Lock Door - AE System	Italy
<i>Rationale:</i> The user needs an overview of a lock and its basic data.			
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the DT Smart Monitor for the user to monitor the door's functional state including a gate failure chance of the lock.			
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to display a model of the lock with its base parameters - The system must be able to display a model of lock doors including the punctual/functional state - The system must display the gate failure chance for lock doors - The system must be able to access required data in order to visualize it 			
<i>Supporting materials:</i>			
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>			
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-FU-IT-22</p>	
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Maintenance alert for users on AE system data	
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>
Functional		Should	
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>
DT Alert System		Lock Door - AE System	Italy
<i>Rationale:</i> For predictive maintenance, a notification shall rise when the current state of a lock door exceeds a given threshold.			
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users on AE system data reaching defined thresholds.			
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when a lock door's state exceeds beyond a given threshold - User must be able to subscribe on a lock's door state with a given threshold 			
<i>Supporting materials:</i>			
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>			
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-23	
Requirement's name		Maintenance alert for users on gate failure predictions	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Should	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario	
DT Alert System	Lock Door - AE System	Italy	
Rationale: For predictive maintenance, a notification shall rise when the gate failure chance of a lock door exceeds a given threshold.			
Requirement description: The system must be able to alert users on gate failure predictions reaching defined threshold.			
Acceptance criteria:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when a gate failure chance exceeds beyond a given threshold - User must be able to subscribe on a lock's door gate failure chance with a given threshold 			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-IT-24	
Requirement's name		Endpoints for accessing pilots' data	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Should	
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario	
DT Controller	Data Accessing on Pilot	Italy	
Rationale: There are various data that needs to be accessed by external systems. For these data, the required endpoints need to be provided.			
Requirement description: The system must provide endpoints needed by external systems.			
Acceptance criteria:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must provide an endpoint to access lock doors state and predictions - The system must provide an endpoint to subscribe to DT Alert System 			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-IT-25</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>	<p>Acquire data of lock chamber dimensions</p>			
<p><i>Category</i></p>	<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>		<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p>Could</p>		
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>Lock Chamber Dimensions</p>		<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> The lock chamber dimension changes due compression by large amounts of water. Therefore, a specification of a real usable lock dimension is required.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive data of lock chamber dimensions.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of width, depth and height of lock chamber dimensions must be possible - The system must be able to store lock chamber dimension - The system must be able to process lock chamber dimension 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-IT-26</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>	<p>Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock chamber dimensions</p>			
<p><i>Category</i></p>	<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>		<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p>Could</p>		
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Lock Chamber Dimensions</p>		<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> The lock chamber dimension changes due compression by large amounts of water. Therefore, a specification of a real usable lock dimension is required.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for the user to display the dimensions of a lock chamber.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain information about lock chamber dimensions. - The system must be able to access lock chamber dimension data in order to visualize it. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-IT-27</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Acquire data about the general lock status</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>General Lock Status</p>		<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> If a lock is not usable for a longer period (e.g., due to maintenance or strike), certain responsible persons and local authorities must be informed. This requires monitoring of this state.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive data about the general lock status.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of general lock status must be possible - The system must be able to store general lock status - The system must be able to process general lock status 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-IT-28</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Navigability alert for users on general lock status</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Alert System</p>		<p>General Lock Status</p>		<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> If a lock is not usable for a longer period (e.g., due to maintenance or strike), certain responsible persons and local authorities must be informed. This requires monitoring of this state.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to notify users on general lock status change.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of a specific general lock status must be possible - Manual input of a duration that a specific general lock status must be kept until a notification occurs must be possible 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier:		REQ-FU-IT-29
Requirement's name		Acquire data about general lock related information indicators		
Category	Type	Priority	Status	
Functional		Could		
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case		Scenario
DT Data Processing		General Information Indicators		Italy
Rationale: A lock has various parameter that are of interest for maintainers and planners.				
Requirement description: The system must be able to receive general information indicators about a lock.				
Acceptance criteria:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of general information indicators must be possible via DT GUI - The system must be able to store data on general information indicators - The system must be able to process lock data (e.g. save) based on general information indicators 				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:		Registration date:

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier:		REQ-FU-IT-30
Requirement's name		Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display general lock related information indicators		
Category	Type	Priority	Status	
Functional		Could		
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case		Scenario
DT Smart Monitor		General Information Indicators		Italy
Rationale: A lock has various parameter that are of interest for maintainers and planners.				
Requirement description: The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for the user to display general lock related information indicators.				
Acceptance criteria:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain general lock related information indicators as key/value pairs - The system must be able to access general information indicators in order to visualize them 				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:		Registration date:

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-IT-31</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Acquire dock related documents</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>Documents</p>		<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> A lock has various documents that are of interest for maintainers and planners.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive documents about a lock.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of documents must be possible - Manual input of additional document related information must be possible - The system must be able to store documents with additional information 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-IT-32</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock related documents</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Documents</p>		<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> A lock has various documents that are of interest for maintainers and planners.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for the user to display lock related documents.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain functionality to access lock related documents - Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain lock related documents additional information - The system must be able to documents and additional information in order to visualize them 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-IT-1</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Lock related document privacy</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>Documents</p>		<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> Security</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The various documents uploaded by maintainers and planners must be held securely.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All documents are encrypted. - Only authorised personal can access the documents. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-IT-2</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Gate failure chance accuracy</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Predictions</p>		<p>Lock Door – AE System</p>		<p>Italy</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The predicted gate failure chance should have a certain accuracy.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The predicted gate failure chance should have a certain accuracy 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier:		REQ-FU-FR-1
Requirement's name		Acquire data of a lock walls punctual state and dimension		
Category	Type	Priority	Status	
Functional		Must		
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case		Scenario
DT Data Processing		Lock Wall - SIR		France
Rationale: A measurement with SIR technology is performed to inspect the walls of a lock. The punctual state and dimension are measured. In future, this data could help to plan inspections and maintenance of lock walls.				
Requirement description: The system must be able to receive data of the functional state and dimension of a lock wall from the subsurface inspection radar.				
Acceptance criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to receive data about the punctual state of a lock wall - The system must be able to receive data about the dimension (height, width, depth (thickness)) of a lock wall 				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:		Registration date:

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier:		REQ-FU-FR-2
Requirement's name		Acquire data on gate failure chance		
Category	Type	Priority	Status	
Functional		Must		
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case		Scenario
DT Data Processing and DT Predictions		Lock Door - AE System		France
Rationale: A measurement with an AE system is performed to inspect the doors of a lock. The functional state and dimension are measured. In future, this data could help to plan inspections and maintenance of lock doors.				
Requirement description: The system must be able to take in data gate failure chance from the acoustic emission system.				
Acceptance criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to receive data about the possible failure chance of a lock door - The system must be able to store the related data - The system must be able to process the related data 				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:		Registration date:

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-FR-3
Requirement's name	Generate Predictions of the gate failure chance	
Category	Type	Priority
Functional		Must
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario
DT Date Processing and DT Predictions	Lock Door - AE System	France
Rationale: A measurement with an AE system is performed to inspect the doors of a lock. The functional state and dimension are measured. In future, this data could help to plan inspections and maintenance of lock doors.		
Requirement description: The system must generate predictions of the gate failure chance using the machine learning module.		
Acceptance criteria: - The system must be able to generate predictions of the gate failure chance within a time period		
Supporting materials:		
Requires ethics observance:		
Source	Identified by:	Registration date:

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-FR-4
Requirement's name	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for visual representation of the lock	
Category	Type	Priority
Functional		Must
Product (Service/Functionality)	Use-case	Scenario
DT Smart Monitor	Lock Door - AE System Lock Wall - SIR	France
Rationale: The user needs an overview of a lock and its basic data.		
Requirement description: The system must provide a GUI using the DT Smart Monitor for the user to monitor the wall's punctual state with dimensions (width, length, depth(thickness)) and the door's functional state including a gate failure chance of the lock.		
Acceptance criteria: - The system must be able to display a model of the lock with its base parameters - The system must be able to display a 3D model of lock walls and lock doors including the punctual/functional state - The system must display the gate failure chance for lock doors - The system must be able to access required data in order to visualize it		
Supporting materials:		

Requires ethics observance:		
<i>Source</i>	<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<i>Requirement's identifier:</i>	REQ-FU-FR-5
<i>Requirement's name</i>	Maintenance alert for users on AE system data		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>
Functional		Must	
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>	<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Alert System	Lock Door - AE System	France	
<i>Rationale:</i> For predictive maintenance, a notification shall rise when the current state of a lock door exceeds a given threshold.			
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users on AR system data reaching defined thresholds.			
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when a lock door's state exceeds beyond a given threshold - User must be able to subscribe on a lock's door state with a given threshold 			
<i>Supporting materials:</i>			
Requires ethics observance:			
<i>Source</i>	<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-6</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Maintenance alert for users on gate failure predictions</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Alert System</p>		<p>Lock Door - AE System</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> For predictive maintenance, a notification shall rise when the gate failure chance of a lock door exceeds a given threshold.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users on gate failure predictions reaching defined thresholds.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when a gate failure chance exceeds beyond a given threshold - User must be able to subscribe on a lock's door gate failure chance with a given threshold 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-7</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Acquire data of lock chamber dimensions</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>Lock Chamber Dimensions</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> The lock chamber dimension changes due compression by large amounts of water. Therefore, a specification of a real usable lock dimension is required.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive data of lock chamber dimensions.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of width, depth and height of lock chamber dimensions must be possible - The system must be able to store lock chamber dimension - The system must be able to process lock chamber dimension 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-8</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>	<p>Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock chamber dimensions</p>			
<p><i>Category</i></p>	<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>		<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p>Should</p>		
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Lock Chamber Dimensions</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> The lock chamber dimension changes due compression by large amounts of water. Therefore, a specification of a real usable lock dimension is required.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for the user to display the dimensions of a lock chamber.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain information about lock chamber dimensions. - The system must be able to access lock chamber dimension data in order to visualize it. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-9</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>	<p>Acquire data about the general lock status</p>			
<p><i>Category</i></p>	<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>		<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p>Could</p>		
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>General Lock Status</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> If a lock is not usable for a longer period (e.g., due to maintenance or strike), certain responsible persons and local authorities must be informed. This requires monitoring of this state.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive data about the general lock status.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of general lock status must be possible - The system must be able to store general lock status - The system must be able to process general lock status 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-10</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Navigability alert for users on general lock status</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Alert System</p>		<p>General Lock Status</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> If a lock is not usable for a longer period (e.g., due to maintenance or strike), certain responsible persons and local authorities must be informed. This requires monitoring of this state.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to notify users on general lock status change.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of a specific general lock status must be possible - Manual input of a duration that a specific general lock status must be kept until a notification occurs must be possible 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-11</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Acquire data about general lock related information indicators</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>General Information Indicators</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> A lock has various parameter that are of interest for maintainers and planners.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive general information indicators about a lock.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of general information indicators must be possible via DT GUI - The system must be able to store data on general information indicators - The system must be able to process data on general information indicators 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-12</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display general lock related information indicators</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p></p>	<p>Could</p>	<p></p>
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>General Information Indicators</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> A lock has various parameter that are of interest for maintainers and planners.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for the user to display general lock related information indicators.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain general lock related information indicators as key/value pairs - The system must be able to access general information indicators in order to visualize them 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>
<p></p>		<p></p>		<p></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-13</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Acquire lock related documents</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p></p>	<p>Could</p>	<p></p>
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>Documents</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> A lock has various documents that are of interest for maintainers and planners.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive documents about a lock.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manual input of documents must be possible - Manual input of additional document related information must be possible - The system must be able to store documents with additional information 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>
<p></p>		<p></p>		<p></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU- FR-14</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock related documents		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Functional		Could		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Smart Monitor		Documents	France	
<i>Rationale:</i> A lock has various documents that are of interest for maintainers and planners.				
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for the user to display lock related documents.				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain functionality to access lock related documents - Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain lock related documents additional information - The system must be able to documents and additional information in order to visualize them 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU- FR 15</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Acquire buoy data		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Data Processing		Buoys	France	
<i>Rationale:</i> A maintenance team shall be sent out for inspection if a buoy moves too far from its intended position. For this purpose, the buoys data must be monitored.				
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to receive buoy data from VNF IOT data hub.				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to receive buoy data from VNF IOT data hub - The system must be able to store data on buoys - The system must be able to process data on buoys 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-16</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display buoys data		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Smart Monitor		Buoys	France	
<i>Rationale:</i> A maintenance team shall be sent out for inspection if a buoy moves too far from its intended position. For this purpose, the buoys data must be monitored.				
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a GUI using the Smart Monitor for the user to display buoys data.				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DT Smart Monitor GUI of the lock must contain buoys data. - The system must be able to access buoys data in order to visualize it. 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-17</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Maintenance alert for users on buoys position data		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Alert System		Buoys	France	
<i>Rationale:</i> A maintenance team shall be sent out for inspection if a buoy moves too far from its intended position. For this purpose, the buoys data must be monitored.				
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users on buoys position exceeding a defined threshold				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when a buoys position changes beyond a given threshold - Users must be able to subscribe on buoys with a given threshold 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier: REQ-FU-FR-18	
Requirement's name		Endpoints for accessing pilots' data	
Category	Type	Priority	Status
Functional		Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case	Scenario
DT Controller		Data Accessing on Pilot	France
Rationale: There are various data that needs to be accessed by external systems. For these data, the required endpoints need to be provided.			
Requirement description: The system must provide endpoints needed by external systems.			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acceptance criteria: The system must provide an endpoint to access lock doors state and predictions - The system must provide an endpoint to access lock walls state - The system must provide an endpoint to get a locks general status - The system must provide an endpoint to set a locks general status The system must provide an endpoint to subscribe to DT Alert System			
Supporting materials:			
Requires ethics observance:			
Source	Identified by:		Registration date:

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-19</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Vision of the current and future state of the network for users		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Functional		Won't Have		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Smart Monitor		Real-time data out of EURIS	France	
<i>Rationale:</i>				
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system could provide a vision of the current and future state of the network (e.g., including opening/closing, hours, unemployment, gauge/service level, water level and others). Real time data could be extracted out of EURIS. Maintenance could be planned out of DT Smart Monitor. The DT provides data about current and future upcoming maintenances.				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-20</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Automatic detection of disorders on complete river		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Functional		Won't Have		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Decision Advice Assistant		Camera based analysis of infrastructures	France	
<i>Rationale:</i>				
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system should detect current state and future maintenance issues using camera detection (e.g., picture or video based). The whole river could be analysed. An AI should detect issues for example like cracks.				
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-21</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Training Testbed for maintenance teams on a virtual lock</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Won't Have</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Maintenance Team Training Assistant</p>		<p>Virtual lock</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> Training maintenance staff is difficult, time-consuming and costly, as external experts often must be engaged.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a functionality for maintenance teams to train change of equipment and inspection on a virtual lock.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p>				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-22</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Decision advice assistant for current and future infrastructure components while consider the overall environment.</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Won't Have</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Decision Advice Assistant</p>		<p>Infrastructure Management Decision Assistant</p>		<p>France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must provide a functionality to simulate some situations to make it easier to decide what is to do in some scenarios. The system should provide assistance on the decision, whether to close or to maintain an existing infrastructure or if the impact in the overall infrastructure would be too significant. The decision should also consider certain KPIs. In addition, the system should provide decision support for the use of new technologies (e.g., the use of a lift instead of a lock).</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p>				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-FR-23</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>	<p>Decision advice assistant for maintenance teams</p>			
<p><i>Category</i></p>	<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>		<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>		<p>Won't Have</p>		
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>	<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>	
<p>DT Decision Advice Assistant</p>	<p>Maintenance Team Decision Advice Assistant</p>		<p>France</p>	
<p><i>Rationale:</i> Currently, external experts must assist in the decision making, which generates additional costs. Decisions are mainly made based by known KPIs such as cost and time.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system should suggest which measures, spare parts, equipment and standard tests to use for upcoming maintenance, repair, damage and inspections. Sometimes there are different solutions and processes for the same issues which have differences in the time and cost impact on the infrastructure.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p>				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-NFU-FR-1</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>	<p>Lock related document privacy</p>			
<p><i>Category</i></p>	<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>		<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Non-functional</p>		<p>Could</p>		
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>	<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>	
<p>DT Data Processing</p>	<p>Documents</p>		<p>France</p>	
<p><i>Rationale:</i> Security</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The various documents uploaded by maintainers and planners must be held securely.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All documents are encrypted. - Only authorised personal can access the documents. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		<i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-NFU-FR-2	
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Gate failure chance accuracy	
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>
Non-functional		Could	
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>	<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Predictions	Lock Door – AE System	France	
<i>Rationale:</i>			
<i>Requirement description:</i> The predicted gate failure chance should have a certain accuracy.			
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>			
- The predicted gate failure chance should have a certain accuracy			
<i>Supporting materials:</i>			
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>			
<i>Source</i>	<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-PO-1</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Acquire data on buoys from GS1 EPCIS</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing</p>		<p>Intelligent Buoys</p>		<p>Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> One of the polish pilots aims is to test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys. This should improve the infrastructure and navigability.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to acquire data on buoys.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to acquire data on buoys - The system must be able to process data on buoys - The system must be able to store processed data on buoys 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-PO-2</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Visualization of a buoys data in DT Smart Monitor</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Intelligent Buoys</p>		<p>Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> One of the polish pilots aims is to test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys. This should improve the infrastructure and navigability.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to visualize a buoys data in DT Smart Monitor.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able visualize a buoys data in DT Smart Monitor - The system must be able to access buoys data in order to visualize it 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-PO-3</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Visualization of a river in DT Smart Monitor</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Smart Monitor</p>		<p>Intelligent Buoys</p>		<p>Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> One of the polish pilots aims is to test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys. This should improve the infrastructure and navigability.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to visualize an area of a river in DT Smart Monitor. A river section with the existing data collected by intelligent buoys is to be display on a kind of map.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to visualize an area of a river in DT Smart Monitor - The system must be able to visualize single data points on an area of a river in DT Smart Monitor. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-PO-4</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Prediction of river conditions</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Data Processing and Predictions</p>		<p>Intelligent Buoys Water Level</p>		<p>Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> One of the polish pilots aims is to test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys. This should improve the infrastructure and navigability.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to generate predictions about the water level at a specific location of a river by a fixed point in time. This could happen by using water level data of upstream estuaries and locations in the river, that are upstream the point under consideration. The data should be collected by intelligent buoys.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to generate predictions on water level using the intelligent buoys data 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-PO-5</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Navigability alert on predicted river conditions		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Alert System		Intelligent Buoys Water Level	Poland	
<p><i>Rationale:</i> One of the polish pilots aims is to test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys. This should improve the infrastructure and navigability.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users when the predicted water level changes beyond a given threshold.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when the predicted water level exceeds beyond a given threshold - Users must be able to subscribe on a predicted water level for a specific location and point in time 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-PO-6</p>
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Navigability alert on current water level		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Functional		Must		
<i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i>		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>	
DT Alert System		Intelligent Buoys Water Level	Poland	
<p><i>Rationale:</i> One of the polish pilots aims is to test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys. This should improve the infrastructure and navigability.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users when the current water level changes beyond a given threshold.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when the current water level exceeds beyond a given threshold - Users must be able to subscribe on a current water level for a specific location and point in time 				
<i>Supporting materials:</i>				
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>				
<i>Source</i>		<i>Identified by:</i>	<i>Registration date:</i>	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-PO-7</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Navigability alert on current ice cover</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Alert System</p>		<p>Intelligent Buoys Ice Cover</p>		<p>Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> One of the polish pilots aims is to test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys. This should improve the infrastructure and navigability.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users when there could be issues due to current ice cover.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when the current ice cover could produce navigability issues - Users must be able to subscribe on current ice cover issues for a specific location and point in time 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-PO-8</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Navigability alert on barge count</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Must</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Alert System</p>		<p>Intelligent Buoys Barge Count</p>		<p>Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> The barge count could provide information about the actual traffic situation on the point under consideration. One of the polish pilots aims is to test IoT technology in real environment based on own buoys. This should improve the infrastructure and navigability.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users when the barge count exceeds or falls below a given threshold.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users must be notified when the barge count exceeds or falls below given thresholds. - Users must be able to subscribe on the barge count with a specific threshold for a given time frame. 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier:		REQ-FU-PO-9
Requirement's name		Endpoints for accessing pilots' data		
Category		Type	Priority	Status
Functional			Must	
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case	Scenario	
DT Controller		Data Accessing on Pilot	Poland	
Rationale: There are various data that needs to be accessed by external systems. For these data, the required endpoints need to be provided.				
Requirement description: The system must provide endpoints needed by external systems.				
- Acceptance criteria: The system must provide an endpoint to subscribe to DT Alert System				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:	Registration date:	

CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		Requirement's identifier:		REQ-NFU-PO-1
Requirement's name		Predicted river condition accuracy		
Category		Type	Priority	Status
Non-functional			Could	
Product (Service/Functionality)		Use-case	Scenario	
DT Predictions		Intelligent Buoys Water Level	Poland	
Rationale:				
Requirement description: The predicted intelligent buoys water level should have a certain accuracy.				
Acceptance criteria:				
- The predicted intelligent buoys water level should have a certain accuracy				
Supporting materials:				
Requires ethics observance:				
Source		Identified by:	Registration date:	

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-CM-1</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Calculate drivable water depth (ship specifications)</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Predictions</p>		<p>River – Water Depth</p>		<p>Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> To contextualize, a maximum ship draught must be calculated.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to calculate the maximum ship draught - The system must be able to use the data - The system must be able to store the processed data 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-CM-2</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Predict drivable water depth (ship specifications)</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Predictions</p>		<p>River – Water Depth</p>		<p>Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> To contextualize, a maximum ship draught must be predicted for a given time.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to predict the maximum ship draught - The system must be able to use the data - The system must be able to store the processed data 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-CM-3</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Navigability alert on drivable water depth (ship specifications)</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Alert System</p>		<p>River – Water Depth</p>		<p>Italy, Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users when the predicted drivable water depth changes.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SCMS must be notified whenever the predicted drivable water depth changes 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-CM-4</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Predict ice cover</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Predictions</p>		<p>Intelligent Buoys Ice Cover</p>		<p>Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The IoT buoy technology of a polish pilot should be used to generate predictions on ice cover height to improve the infrastructure and navigability. For example, based on existing data, predictions could be made about adjacent river ice cover development.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to predict the ice cover - The system must be able to use the data - The system must be able to store the processed data 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-CM-5</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Navigability alert on predicted ice cover</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Could</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Alert System</p>		<p>Intelligent Buoys Ice Cover</p>		<p>Poland</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i> The SCMS could use information on ice cover height to improve logistical planning.</p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert SCMS when there could be issues due to predicted ice cover.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The SCMS must be notified when the predicted ice cover could produce navigability issues 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

<p>CRISTAL REQUIREMENT</p>		<p><i>Requirement's identifier:</i></p>		<p>REQ-FU-CM-6</p>
<p><i>Requirement's name</i></p>		<p>Determine maintenance duration based on static table (AE-System)</p>		
<p><i>Category</i></p>		<p><i>Type</i></p>	<p><i>Priority</i></p>	<p><i>Status</i></p>
<p>Functional</p>			<p>Should</p>	
<p><i>Product (Service/Functionality)</i></p>		<p><i>Use-case</i></p>		<p><i>Scenario</i></p>
<p>DT Predictions</p>		<p>Lock Door</p>		<p>Italy, France</p>
<p><i>Rationale:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requirement description:</i> To contextualize, a category of infrastructure maintenance or failure must be tied to a downtime duration. The information about the infrastructure event comes from the AE-System and a static table.</p>				
<p><i>Acceptance criteria:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The system must be able to determine the downtime data - The system must be able to use the data - The system must be able to store the processed data 				
<p><i>Supporting materials:</i></p>				
<p><i>Requires ethics observance:</i></p>				
<p><i>Source</i></p>		<p><i>Identified by:</i></p>		<p><i>Registration date:</i></p>

 CRISTAL REQUIREMENT		<i>Requirement's identifier:</i> REQ-FU-CM-7	
<i>Requirement's name</i>		Maintenance alert on lock door downtime	
<i>Category</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Priority</i>	<i>Status</i>
Functional		Should	
<i>Product</i> (Service/Functionality)		<i>Use-case</i>	<i>Scenario</i>
DT Alert System		Lock door	Italy, France
<i>Rationale:</i>			
<i>Requirement description:</i> The system must be able to alert users when a downtime is foreseeable and how long it will take.			
<i>Acceptance criteria:</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SCMS must be notified whenever a downtime is foreseeable - SCMS must be provided with the maintenance duration 			
<i>Supporting materials:</i>			
<i>Requires ethics observance:</i>			
<i>Source</i>	<i>Identified by:</i>		<i>Registration date:</i>